

Restore4Life

RESTORING WETLANDS
FOR A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE

D4.3 REPORT ON NBS BUSINESS SUPPORT FRAMEWORK

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D4.3 REPORT ON NBS BUSINESS SUPPORT FRAMEWORK

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Abstract	This Deliverable Report marks the end of the half-way point in the R4L implementation period. Within WP4, we have collected all the PESTLE data, organised all nine of the planned stakeholder workshops, conducted 21 interviews with business organisations at all of the R4L study sites, and prepared detailed studies on measuring and valuing biodiversity and an economic cost benefit analysis for establishing a fish spawning site.
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Abbreviations

AHP	Analytic Hierarchy Process
AR	Associated Region
CICES	Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services
EIB	European Investment Bank
EEA	European Environment Agency
ES	Ecosystem services
IS	Implementation Site
NbS	Nature-based solutions
MSME	Micro-, Small-, and Medium-size Enterprises
PESTLE	Politics, Economy, Social, Technical, Legislation, Environment
SME	Micro- small- and medium sized business ¹
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats analysis

¹ According to Commission Recommendation 2003/361/EC: micro, small or medium-sized enterprise (SME) are enterprises

- engaged in an economic activity, irrespective of their legal form (including, in particular, self-employed persons and family businesses engaged in craft or other activities, and partnerships or associations regularly engaged in an economic activity) and
- employing fewer than 250 persons (expressed in 'annual working units' as defined in Article 5 of the Recommendation) and which have an annual turnover not exceeding EUR 50 million, and/or an annual balance sheet total not exceeding EUR 43 million.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Deliverable Report marks the end of the half-way point in the R4L implementation period. Within WP4, we have collected all the PESTLE data, organised all nine of the planned stakeholder workshops, conducted 21 interviews with business organisations at all of the R4L study sites, and prepared detailed studies on measuring and valuing biodiversity and an economic cost benefit analysis for establishing a fish spawning site.

From this work, we have gained a detailed insight into the socioeconomic conditions around the R4L study sites. The PESTLE analyses showed that the relative importance of various socio-economic and environmental factors was broadly similar in all countries but also quite distinct at the site level and were mostly negative for SME development.

From the interviews we constructed a matrix for business opportunities based on wetland ecosystem services as well as public goods. These ranged from micro to large size, encompassing farming, fish production, reed harvesting, forestry, water management, power generation, and tourism sectors. Restored wetlands form a category of nature-based solutions that, among other services, provide opportunities to conduct various ecologically sustainable business activities due to their specific aquatic and moist terrestrial features including regenerative biomass, food production, capacity for carbon sequestration, habitat quality and diversity, and potential for tourism. In the context of sustainable economic activities and revenue generation, NbS businesses contribute directly to Criterion 4 of the IUCN Global Standard that NbS should be economically viable.

However, owing to their small area and/or protected status, none of the study sites had people living within them so there were no directly concerned local communities. Some general features of businesses operating in the vicinity of the study sites were:

- Finding relevant local businesses and arranging interviews with them proved difficult largely due to the small scale of the sites (so few businesses present) and also an occasional lack of willingness to meet.
- Although tourism development is often proposed as a potential business opportunity in the wetland restoration areas, the existing tourism businesses are struggling to achieve their potential following the Covid epidemic and the impact of Russia invading Ukraine.
- Structural issues such as rural depopulation, land ownership and unreformed natural resource use and environmental policies have significant implications for the adoption of NbS approaches by local businesses.
- The visits raised awareness of the existing and potential benefits (tangible and intangible) from implementing NbS in relation to wetland restoration at the implementation sites by deploying project expertise to assist the local businesses.
- Private sector funds are not yet ready to invest in NbS business development, especially for SMEs. The transaction costs, unfamiliar risk profiles, lack of scale-up opportunities, and low (or no) profits and liquidity all mitigate against such financing so that today

nearly all NbS businesses are relatively small scale (individual or friends-and-family funded) or supported by state-owned companies.

From these findings, we have constructed a general SWOT analysis of the situation of SMEs conducting or attempting to establish financially viable businesses in and around natural and semi-natural wetlands. These and other resources will be further analysed and reported in the next deliverable report 4.2 on NbS Economic Options Guidance, due at the end of April 2026, leading to the next stage of R4L WP4 outputs in the second half of the R4L implementation period, including:

- development of wetland NbS business models and investment frameworks;
- creation of an NbS business potential index;
- elaboration of site-based assessments linking biodiversity conservation with local economic opportunities;
- preparation of policy guidance and tutorials to support entrepreneurs entering biodiversity-friendly markets.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Restore4life project (Restoration of wetland complexes as life-supporting systems in the Danube Basin) is a Horizon Europe funded project that supports the EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters. The Mission aims to protect and restore the health of our ocean and waters through research and innovation, citizen engagement and blue investments. The Mission's holistic approach will address the ocean and waters as one system and play a key role in achieving climate neutrality and restoring nature.

Restore4Life aims to develop a "Restore4Life Wetland Restoration Decision Support System" at the Danube Basin level. The service will be based on a shared vision for wetland restoration, including co-creation and co-development of tools that will allow local stakeholders and actors to be actively involved in restoration works and help local businesses adopt new activities through nature-based solutions supported by new generation of data analysis tools.

Within the context of the overall Restore4Life (R4L) project, Work Package 4 seeks to stimulate local enterprises to adopt nature-based solutions derived from the wetlands restored by the project, through:

- exploring regional framework settings, development options, comparative advantages and limitations of local sustainable use of restored wetlands;
- increasing the share of / support for ecologically sustainable business activities in restored wetland ecosystems that adopt nature-based solutions for economic diversification, increased labour skills and long-term local revenue generation;
- supporting increased labour skills and long-term local revenue generation;
- contributing business related modules to the web-based Restore4Life Wetland Restoration Support Platform.

This report represents a stock-take of several of activities implemented in the first three of the four tasks contained in the Work Package, conducted from the start of R4L on 1 June 2023 to 31 July 2025. These are outlined below, while the final Task 4.4 on modules for business policy design contributing to the Restore4Life Wetland Restoration Support Platform is the subject of the remaining project period.

Task 4.1 Regional capacity and marketing research for sustainable business

Wetlands provide opportunities to conduct ecologically sustainable business due to their outstanding aquatic and terrestrial biomass and food production, capacity for carbon sequestration, habitat quality and diversity, and potential for tourism. To assess the local socioeconomic conditions and essential business capacity and support infrastructures in each of the Implementation and Associated Region sites, a range of relevant stakeholders, including SME owners and/or managers, were invited to workshops where part of the agenda was to carry out a PESTLE analysis (an evaluation of political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legal factors) The initial results for Implementation Sites were presented

in the Deliverable 9 report on Regional Capacity: Stakeholder Pestle Analysis uploaded in November 2023.

Task 4.2 Economic and business options based on NbS

In summer 2024 and summer 2025, SME owners and/or managers associated with Implementation and Associated Region sites were contacted and interviewed (all except one in person) to identify local business needs and opportunities and compile a site-specific catalogue of applicable business-related NbS (see the Milestone 18 report on Matrix of Potential Wetland NbS Benefits at Implementation Sites uploaded in September 2024). In addition, a seventh Monitoring Site was established at Fokorúpuszta in Hungary to carry out an in-depth cost benefit analysis for setting up a fish spawning site as a model for other floodplain sites in the Danube Basin.

Task 4.3 Business support framework embedding wetland restoration into the local economy

This Task is the main focus of this report. It builds on the previous two by expanding and analysing the information collected in relation to accepted business support frameworks related to wetland restoration as a nature-based solution (NbS). Activities comprised:

- (a) development of a rapid assessment approach for estimating local economic benefits from biodiversity based on existing methodologies for measuring and valuing biodiversity in order to establish a harmonised approach most applicable for restored wetlands (see Section 4);
- (b) assessing the potential for aggregating businesses within societal support structures such as chambers of commerce, clusters, land trusts, cooperatives, foundations and associations;
- (c) investigating with local authorities the establishment of regional marketing organisations to brand and promote local products and services resulting from wetland site restoration, as well as serving as an innovation hub to incubate and assemble new business investment pipelines;
- (d) engaging with investors looking for targeted green investments to understand their requirements and potential interest in supporting NbS businesses such as fish spawning grounds (see Section 5).

2 BUSINESS DATA COLLECTION METHODS

This section sets out the range of R4L wetland restoration sites included in the study and details of the methods used to collect business-related data from them.

2.1 Wetland Restoration Sites

Three categories of wetland sites were involved in the study (Figure 1 and Table 1):

- Implementation Sites within the Danube River basin and Black Sea coastal region where R4L partners are actively involved in research, design and implementation of wetland restoration measures;
- Associated Region sites where “cascade” funding from R4L was made available after an open call for proposals to support five wetland restoration initiatives in the wider EU neighbourhood;
- Monitoring Sites, which originally comprised six sites, where wetland restoration was carried out previously and serve as baselines for assessing intervention outcomes; however, for the specific purposes of WP4, a seventh Monitoring Site was established at Fokorúpuszta in Hungary (Section 5).

Figure 1: Location of R4L Study Sites

Table 1: Brief overview of R4L Study Sites

Code, Name	Features	
IS 1 Austria / Slovakia: March - Thaya Floodplains	River-floodplain systems with various side arms and backwaters, floodplain forests. Re-opening of a former channel to restore flow to an internal lake.	
IS 2 Slovakia: Rudava River	Tributary of March River; floodplain with oxbow lakes. Restoration of flow in a former river channel.	
IS 3 Serbia: Vlasina Lake	River floodplain with wet meadows, transition mires and tall herbs. Restoration of transition mires through clearing invasive scrub and rewetting.	
IS 4 Romania: Enisala Channel	Part of Razim lagoon at Enisala, a key spawning area for zander <i>Sander lucioperca</i> . Restoration of fish spawning area through dredging silt from the channel.	
AR 1 Armenia: Armash fish ponds	A former fish pond that will be rewetted with a mosaic of wet habitats to attract breeding and migratory birds, with a hide and information boards for birdwatchers	
AR 2 Belgium: Grote Meers	A lowland fen that is gradually drying out. The old drainage channels will be altered and a small sluice installed to raise the water table. Photo: K. Buysse	

Code, Name	Features	
AR 3 Portugal: Lagoas de Bertandos e São Pedro d'Arcos	The floodplain woodland is being invaded by exotic tree species, especially acacia. The trees will be ring-barked to prevent further spread.	
AR 4 Sweden: Svensksundsviken streams	Altered stream channels will be re-profiled to restore the original meanders and natural flow regime.	
AR 5 Ukraine: Bilohorshcha fen	The fen is drying out because of drainage. The drains will be blocked to raise water levels which will also impede the spread of scrub and birch.	
MS MS7 7 Hungary: floodplain at Fokorúpuszta	Wet reseeded meadow pasture and shallow water suitable for use as a fish spawning area.	

2.2 PESTLE assessments

The background and methodology for PESTLE assessments are described in the Deliverable 9 Report on Regional Capacity: Stakeholder Pestle Analysis (November 2023). The main advance here is that five further stakeholder group PESTLE assessments were carried out in the Associated Region sites. Furthermore, the approach was amended so that whereas scores for different PESTLE factors were counted at IS workshops by show of hands, for the AR sites (AR) a paper form was used and individuals recorded their scores in it. Future analysis of the results will explore whether the different recording methods led to significant differences in scoring. It should also be noted that the workshop participants were not a random selection representative of a population but a selected subset relating to the location of and activities at the study sites as known to the local coordinators.

In addition, for the AR sites the weighting of the relative importance of the various PESTLE factors was assessed using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP). AHP is a decision-making

method used by individuals and organisations to rank alternatives they are considering based on pairwise comparisons². The method will also be applied to the IS in the near future.

2.3 Business Interviews

A structured interview sheet (Table 2) was prepared to collect basic business data as well as more general information about business activities and their relationships with the wetland restoration plans at the R4L study sites. It was designed to mirror a formal Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats (SWOT) analysis but be conversational rather than intimidating for the interviewee. Key businesses at each site were identified by the local site coordinators. The interviews were conducted mostly in person at the business premises.

Table 2: Structured Interview Sheet for Local Businesses

Question	SWOT aspects
Date of interview	
Place of interview	
Country	
Format of interview (in person, online)	
R4L site	
What is the legal name of the business	
When was the company formed	
Economic sector	
What is your name and function in the business	
What is the web site of the business	
Please can you describe the activities of the business, especially concerning the [site name] area	S
How large is the company: micro (1 - 9 employees); small (10 - 49); medium (50 - 249); large	S, W
What is the ownership structure of the business: state owned; listed on a stock market; private shareholders; sole private owner; other	S, W
Do you plan to grow the business in the next few years, especially around the site	O
What are the main problems for operating your business	T
Does your company have an environmental policy (please supply a copy)	S, W, O
Do you know about the EU-funded wetland restoration project at the site	O
What benefits do you think you could gain from the restoration work	O
Do you have any questions for us	

² T.L. Saaty (1980) *The Analytic Hierarchy Process: Planning, Priority Setting, Resource Allocation*. 287pp. McGraw-Hill New York

3 RESULTS ABOUT THE BUSINESS SITUATION IN R4L WETLAND SITES

3.1 PESTLE Assessments

The number of R4L study site workshop participants that took part in PESTLE assessments was between 125 and 141 (Table 3). For the IS, only aggregated data is available because of the show of hands approach, while for the AR individual data sets are available. For aggregated data, there are 9 sites x 46 PESTLE elements x 6 score categories giving a total of 2,484 data points before applying the AHP weights (see below). All the data has been entered in to a PESTLE data base for investigation using multi-criteria analysis techniques to isolate key PESTLE elements to be considered for business development in or near wetlands as part of WP4.4.

Table 3: Number of R4L study site workshop participants that took part in PESTLE assessments

Locality	Date of WS	PESTLE respondents
IS 1 Austria / Slovakia: March - Thaya Floodplains	02/11/2023	16
IS 2 Slovakia: Rudava River	31/10/2023	26, 16 after lunch
IS 3 Serbia: Vlasina Lake	25/10/2023	16
IS 4 Romania: Enisala Channel	20/10/2023	17
AR 1 Armenia: Armash fish ponds	02/11/2023	16
AR 2 Belgium: Grote Meers	18/06/2025	14
AR 3 Portugal: Lagoas de Bertandos e São Pedro d'Arcos	07/05/2025	21
AR 4 Sweden: Svensksundsviken streams	27/05/2025	10
AR 5 Ukraine: Bilohorshcha fen	25/06/2025	15

125 – 141

A preliminary AHP of the relative importance of PESTLE factors at the AR study sites was also undertaken (Figure 2). The variation in weights between the five sites is quite large suggesting that wetland stakeholders as such are not a uniform group and therefore socioeconomic studies should be done on a case-by-case basis.

Figure 2: Group weights of PESTLE factors at the five AR study sites

3.2 Business Interviews

A total of 21 confidential interviews were conducted with businesses or economic operators with some connection to the R4L study sites. These are summarised in Table 4, with more details provided in Annexes A and B. The identities of the companies and interviewees have been withheld for reasons of personal and business data protection.

Table 4: Business interviews conducted

Site	Sector	Date of Interview	Potential benefits from site restoration
IS 1 Austria / Slovakia: March - Thaya Floodplains	Farming, Forestry, Angling	18/07/24	Opportunity to involve the site area in the development of European OECMs.
IS 2 Slovakia: Rudava River	Fisheries	16/07/24	Opportunity for local stakeholder participation in monitoring fish community development through a local angling group
IS 2 Slovakia: Rudava River	Water management	17/07/24	Opportunity to influence the next national water plan to introduce more NbS approaches. The positive role of beavers in water management could be highlighted.
IS 2 Slovakia: Rudava River	Farming	17/07/24	Opportunity to collaborate closely with the business and use as a model for other floodplain farmers.
IS 3 Serbia: Vlasina Lake	Tourism	09/07/24	Potential to provide expertise for ecotourism development plan and site promotion as a destination
IS 3 Serbia: Vlasina Lake	Energy	10/07/24	Opportunity to engage the company with project implementation (corporate sponsorship). Potential to advise on measures to stabilise eroding shorelines to prevent peat entering the lake and reduce peat loss
IS 4 Romania: Enisala Channel	Farming	23/07/24	Opportunity to help develop agrotourism / angling (a similar operation is located nearby), and adopt drought-prone farming practices.
IS 4 Romania: Enisala Channel	Tourism	23/07/24	Opportunity to develop water-based tourism activities, and good facilities for group activities - retreats, seminars, sports.
IS 4 Romania: Enisala Channel	Tourism, Reed harvesting	24/07/24 (Online)	Opportunity to develop reed harvesting operation at Enisala and collaborate with the Danube Delta National Institute.
AR 1 Armenia: Armash fish ponds	Fish production	06/06/25	Opportunity to attract and accommodate birdwatchers
AR 1 Armenia: Armash fish ponds	Tourism	05/06/25	Opportunity to develop new nature tourism offer
AR 1 Armenia: Armash fish ponds	Tourism	05/06/25	Opportunity to develop new nature tourism offer
AR 1 Armenia: Armash fish ponds	Tourism	05/06/25	Opportunity to develop new nature tourism offer
AR 1 Armenia: Armash fish ponds	Tourism	05/06/25	Opportunity to develop new nature tourism offer
AR 2 Belgium: Grote Meers	Water management	19/06/25	Opportunity to demonstrate water management technology
AR 2 Belgium: Grote Meers	Water management	16/06/25	Opportunity to demonstrate water management technology
AR 3 Portugal: Lagoas de Bertandos e São Pedro d'Arcos	Tourism	08/05/25	Opportunity to develop new nature tourism offer
AR 3 Portugal: Lagoas de Bertandos e São Pedro d'Arcos	Tourism	09/05/25	Opportunity to develop new nature tourism offer
AR 3 Portugal: Lagoas de Bertandos e São Pedro d'Arcos	Agriculture	09/05/25	Opportunity to expand organic beef production
AR 4 Sweden: Svensksundsviken streams	Agriculture	26/05/25	Opportunity to obtain more secure water supply
AR 4 Sweden: Svensksundsviken streams	Agriculture	26/05/25	Unclear
AR 5 Ukraine: Bilohorshcha fen	Food processing	24/06/25	Opportunity to develop branded products

4 MEASURING AND VALUING BIODIVERSITY

This section is based on the Milestone Report 19 on Review of Methodologies for Measuring and Valuing Biodiversity (November 2024) in the context of the design of financial instruments supporting biodiversity and ways for businesses to assess their ecological footprint.

The review addresses the urgent need to integrate climate change mitigation, biodiversity protection, and nature-based solutions into business practices. Businesses increasingly recognise biodiversity loss as a financial risk, while regulators push for biodiversity-related disclosures and risk management. The different aspects of business involvement in NbS can be summarised in a SWOT Analysis (Table 5).

Table 5: SWOT analysis of business involvement in NbS

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> growing adoption of corporate social responsibility advanced biodiversity monitoring using GIS and remote sensing innovative financing mechanisms like biodiversity credits and Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES) increasing engagement with NbS, such as wetland restoration and sustainable agriculture, which deliver both ecological and economic benefits 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> limited awareness of biodiversity impacts short-term financial priorities inconsistent data and metrics difficulties coordinating with governments and NGOs
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> rising consumer demand for sustainable products increased investor focus on environmental, social and governance (ESG) issues rapid growth in sustainable finance expanding markets for ecosystem services and biodiversity-friendly certification schemes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> biodiversity risks often remain undervalued or externalised “greenwashing” practices can undermine genuine biodiversity commitments political and market instability can deter long-term biodiversity investment

4.1 Tools and Frameworks for Measuring Biodiversity

There are strong legal and institutional drivers that impel governments and businesses to consider biodiversity conservation and NbS in legal frameworks and business operations. These include international conventions such as the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species (CITES), Ramsar Convention on Wetlands, Convention on Migratory Species, and the EU Birds and Habitats Directives. These frameworks set legal obligations and support biodiversity action although they face uneven enforcement, limited resources, and varying political commitment.

In recent decades, four main categories of tools have been developed to improve the application of legal instruments for biodiversity conservation and NbS (Figure 3). However, they face several common challenges that hinder their effectiveness:

- Data gaps and lack of standardised metrics across sectors and regions.
- Technical complexity and resource intensity of biodiversity monitoring and valuation.
- Limited stakeholder engagement, especially among small and medium enterprises.
- Need to better integrate biodiversity metrics into broader economic and environmental assessments.
- Risk that biodiversity remains underrepresented in environmental impact assessments and business risk strategies

4.1.1 Biodiversity assessment tools

These tools evaluate biodiversity conditions, threats and trends. Examples include:

- Biodiversity Indicators Partnership (BIP): provides standardised indicators for tracking progress toward biodiversity goals, though dependent on data availability and quality.
- Global Biodiversity Outlook (GBO): CBD's periodic biodiversity status report, useful for policy but limited by data timeliness .
- IUCN Red List: key for identifying threatened species but affected by inconsistencies in data collection .

Other approaches include rapid biodiversity assessments and biodiversity hotspot mapping. These provide useful decision support but may lack granularity, consistency, or integration with socio-economic data.

4.1.2 Ecosystem Services Assessment Tools

These tools, such as, support land-use and conservation planning. They include InVEST, LandScale and the River Ecosystem Service Index.

4.1.3 Biodiversity Measuring Tools

These quantify biodiversity elements, such as species diversity or ecosystem integrity. Examples include:

- Ecological Footprint: measures human resource consumption but not biodiversity health .
- Shannon Index and similar metrics: quantify species diversity but oversimplify ecological complexity and ignore functional diversity .
- Habitat Quality Indices, Species Richness & Evenness measures: useful but limited by subjective assessments.
- Biodiversity Impact Metric (BIM): used by industries to track raw material sourcing impacts .
- Agrobiodiversity Index which assesses biodiversity in agriculture.
- Global Biodiversity Score (GBS): a company-wide biodiversity footprint metric.

4.1.4 Biodiversity Management Tools

These tools guide the planning and implementation of biodiversity actions:

- Integrated Coastal Zone Management (ICZM) and Ecosystem-Based Management (EBM): balance development and ecosystem needs but face institutional and stakeholder challenges.
- Conservation Easements & Biodiversity Offset Schemes: protect or replace biodiversity but raise issues of equivalency and monitoring.
- Marine Protected Areas (MPAs): effective but limited by enforcement and funding.
- Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES): align economic and ecological interests but depend on sustainable financing and clear metrics.
- Certification schemes (e.g., FSC, MSC, RSPO, RSB, Better Cotton) promote sustainable production but can be costly for smaller producers .
- Wildlife corridors, ecological restoration, community-based conservation: enhance connectivity and ecosystem health, but success depends on governance and resources .

Figure 3: Relations between governance drivers and measuring biodiversity values

4.2 Outlook and Applications

The review on measuring and valuing biodiversity concludes that successful integration of biodiversity into financial and business systems requires:

- standardised and widely adopted biodiversity metrics;
- improved collaboration among businesses, governments, and civil society;
- innovative financing mechanisms such as biodiversity credits;
- stronger legal frameworks with robust enforcement; and
- education and awareness to increase business capacity for biodiversity action.

5 FOKORÚPUSZTA FISH SPAWNING SITE CASE STUDY

5.1 Background

The case study presented in Annex C provides a detailed example of how three types of economic organisation (a state water management company, an angling association and a National Park administration) can collaborate to elicit various ecosystem services from a realignment of a floodplain embankment at Fokorúpuszta in the Middle Tisza region of Hungary (Figure 1 and Table 1). It evaluates the integration of natural floodplain spawning grounds into fishery management to determine whether operating such spawning grounds can be economically self-sustaining while delivering ecological and social benefits.

The analysis assesses the economic feasibility of operating the spawning ground, examines the legal and institutional arrangements needed for long-term management and support is the creation of a stakeholder cooperation agreement. A central assumption is that economic sustainability is necessary for environmental sustainability, meaning interventions that are not financially viable risk eventual failure.

Floodplain restoration and spawning areas can create diverse ecosystem services such as:

- flood risk reduction (through increased retention);
- biodiversity gains (habitats for fish, amphibians, and waterbirds);
- climate regulation (cooling via evaporation and improved microclimate); and
- agricultural and recreational benefits (grazing opportunities, improved angling).

In addition, at Fokorúpuszta, floodplain restoration enabled the creation of a semi-natural fish spawning habitat of about 23 ha (after earth was removed to create a new embankment) that can:

- provide low-cost natural reproduction, reducing dependence on artificial fish stocking;
- enhance ecosystem complexity and resilience; and
- support angling and biodiversity goals simultaneously.

5.2 Economic Cost Benefit Analysis

The key stakeholders in this initiative are:

- KÖTIVIZIG – a Water Management Authority that focuses on flood safety, land management, and infrastructure maintenance;
- KÖTIHESZ – an Anglers' Association that seeks abundant fish populations for recreational angling; and
- HNPI – the Fertő-Hanság National Park Directorate that prioritises nature conservation.

Hungarian law mandates that annual fish stocking (principally of carp) must be undertaken to maintain a minimum level of fish populations impacted by angling. While this law limits the ability to replace artificial stocking entirely with natural reproduction, natural spawning can reduce additional stocking costs beyond the legal minimum which is a benefit for anglers. Research has shown that one hectare of spawning ground can replace stocking on ten hectares of river surface.

The spawning ground's operating costs (maintenance, monitoring, fish sorting, invasive species removal, infrastructure operation) are estimated at HUF 1.95–2.97 million/year, equivalent to 85,000–130,000 HUF/ha. After a successful spawning event, the cost of replenishing fish stocks using natural spawning of some 300,000 fingerlings is 8,500–13,000 HUF³/ha of river surface, compared to 41,000–52,000 HUF/ha for stocked juvenile fish.

Because spawning success varies with hydrological conditions, four scenarios were evaluated:

- Annual success: clear cost advantage for natural spawning.
- Success every 3 years: still significantly cheaper than artificial stocking.
- Success every 5 years: similar or slightly better than stocking.
- Success every 10 years: comparable cost but less reliable.

Even with conservative biological assumptions (low fry survival and low market value), spawning every 3–5 years is cost-competitive, with a positive net economic value. However, the evaluations excluded the sunk investment costs of the original flood mitigation project of about HUF 1.1 billion funded by public money, not by anglers' associations. If future sites had to be financed privately, costs would exceed benefits unless additional funding (e.g. EU restoration grants) is secured. Thus, new sites may not be economically feasible solely on fishery grounds, but repurposing existing or planned restoration works is attractive.

5.3 Framework Cooperation Agreement

While all the key stakeholders support spawning sites in principle, some conflicts exist:

- there are different priorities on invasive species management and timing of fish releases;
- there is potential disturbance from angling near spawning grounds; and
- bird predation of fry, which conservationists value but anglers see as competition.

To address these issues, a framework cooperation agreement is recommended, based on previous successful examples (e.g. at Doba) whereby:

- anglers manage the spawning site free of charge;
- the Water Management Authority shares flood forecasting data to optimise timing;

³ 1 HUF = €0.0025 in July 2025

- joint monitoring programmes are undertaken to assess fish populations and ecological status;
- the Agreement includes rules for invasive species control, habitat management, and annual operational planning.

The approach can be extended to other floodplain habitats, supporting Hungary's broader ecosystem services valuation framework and aligning with EU Green Deal goals.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This Deliverable Report marks the end of the half-way point in the R4L implementation period. Within WP4, we have collected all the PESTLE data, organised all nine of the planned stakeholder workshops, conducted 21 interviews with business organisations at all of the R4L study sites, and prepared detailed studies on measuring and valuing biodiversity and an economic cost benefit analysis for establishing a fish spawning site.

From this work, we have gained a detailed insight into the socioeconomic conditions around the R4L study sites. The PESTLE analyses showed that the relative importance of various socio-economic and environmental factors was broadly similar in all countries but also quite distinct at the site level and were mostly negative for SME development.

From the interviews we constructed a matrix for business opportunities based on wetland ecosystem services as well as public goods. These ranged from micro to large size, encompassing farming, fish production, reed harvesting, forestry, water management, power generation, and tourism sectors (Table 6). Restored wetlands form a category of nature-based solutions that, among other services, provide opportunities to conduct various ecologically sustainable business activities due to their specific aquatic and moist terrestrial features including regenerative biomass, food production, capacity for carbon sequestration, habitat quality and diversity, and potential for tourism. In the context of sustainable economic activities and revenue generation, NbS businesses contribute directly to Criterion 4 of the IUCN Global Standard⁴ that NbS should be economically viable.

However, owing to their small area and/or protected status, none of the study sites had people living within them so there were no directly concerned local communities. Some general features of businesses operating in the vicinity of the study sites were:

- Finding relevant local businesses and arranging interviews with them proved difficult largely due to the small scale of the sites (so few businesses present) and also an occasional lack of willingness to meet.
- Although tourism development is often proposed as a potential business opportunity in the wetland restoration areas, the existing tourism businesses are struggling to achieve their potential following the Covid epidemic and the impact of Russia invading Ukraine.
- Structural issues such as rural depopulation, land ownership and unreformed natural resource use and environmental policies have significant implications for the adoption of NbS approaches by local businesses.
- The visits raised awareness of the existing and potential benefits (tangible and intangible) from implementing NbS in relation to wetland restoration at the implementation sites by deploying project expertise to assist the local businesses.

⁴ <https://portals.iucn.org/library/sites/library/files/documents/2020-020-En.pdf>

Table 6: NbS business opportunities from wetland ecosystem services at R4L sites

Cells shaded blue are opportunities for NbS businesses; existing economic activities are shown in bold lettering
Unshaded cells are additional services provided as public goods

Ecosystem service category	Ecosystem service division	Business potential	Direct	Indirect	IS 1 AU/SK: March - Thaya Floodplains	IS 2 SK: Rudava River	IS 3 RS: Vlasina Lake	IS 4 RO: Enisala Channel	AR 1 AM: Armash fish ponds	AR 2 BE: Grote Meers	AR 3 PT: Lagoas	AR 4 SE: Svensk streams	AR 5 UA: Biloehorsicha fen
Cultural (Abiotic)	Direct, in-situ and outdoor interactions with natural physical systems	Recreation; ecotourism; wellness	x	x			Visitors	Visitors	Visitors	Visitors			Visitors
Provisioning (Abiotic)	Water	Potable water in public supply system; mineral water; glass house cultivation; hydropower; tidal power	x										
Provisioning (Biotic)	Biomass	Reared or wild plant and animal food; dietary supplements; pharmaceuticals; clothing; cosmetics; jewellery; fuel; renewable energy; timber; construction materials	x	x	Fishing Timber Forest products	Fishing		Fishing Reed harvesting	Fishing		Timber Forest products	Fishing	Fishing Reed harvesting
Regulation & Maintenance (Abiotic)	Regulation of physical, chemical, biological conditions	Reduction in damage costs by regulation of baseline flows and extreme events	x		Floodplain expansion	Flood relief				Flood relief			
Regulation & Maintenance (Biotic)	Transformation of biochemical or physical inputs to ecosystems	Mediation of waste, toxics and other nuisances by non-living processes	x	x				Reduction of algal blooms					
Regulation & Maintenance (Biotic)	Transformation of biochemical or physical inputs to ecosystems	Sustainable disposal of wastes; decomposition by micro-organisms, algae, plants and animals	x	x	Floodplain expansion	Floodplain expansion							
Regulation & Maintenance (Biotic)	Regulation of physical, chemical, biological conditions	Maintaining nursery habitats; reduced nutrient runoff from agro-ecosystems; maintenance of soil quality; reduction in fire damage costs	x	x	Fish spawning habitat Reduction of nutrient run-off	Floodplain expansion Reduction of nutrient run-off	Increase of peat formation Amphibian spawning ponds	Fish spawning habitat Reed beds		Reduction of nutrient run-off			

- Private sector funds are not yet ready to invest in NbS business development, especially for SMEs. The transaction costs, unfamiliar risk profiles, lack of scale-up opportunities, and low (or no) profits and liquidity all mitigate against such financing so that today nearly all NbS businesses are relatively small scale (individual or friends-and-family funded) or supported by state-owned companies.

From these findings, we have constructed a general SWOT analysis of the situation of SMEs conducting or attempting to establish financially viable businesses in and around natural and semi-natural wetlands (Table 7).

Table 7: SWOT analysis of wetland-related SME business situation

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Land ownership or rights (private or state) over all the site • Benefits for local communities e.g. employment, infrastructure, revival of ecosystem services • Wide variety of potential viable and sustainable business activities (Table 6) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial system not ready to invest • No revenue from intangible (cultural) ES • Lack of overview of market to set prices • Low profit margins • Lack of assets for collateral • Lack of suitable staff • Lack of accommodation and services for visitors • Lack of involvement in restoration consultations
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expansion including export markets • Investment in better skills and machinery • Establishment of cooperatives, clusters • Improvement of processing and product quality • Obtain appropriate nature protection status e.g. OECM, local nature reserve • Concessions for other users 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate change • Deterioration / loss of ecosystem services • Bureaucratic hurdles and protected area regulations • Changes in CAP payments • Water pollution • Eutrophication / algal growth • Water management infrastructure • Epidemics • Conflicts and insecurity • Invasive species (invertebrates, fish, plants) • Competition from other tourist destinations

These and other resources will be further analysed and reported in the next deliverable report 4.2 on NbS Economic Options Guidance, due at the end of April 2026, leading to the next stage of R4L WP4 outputs in the second half of the R4L implementation period, including:

- development of wetland NbS business models and investment frameworks;
- creation of an NbS business potential index;
- elaboration of site-based assessments linking biodiversity conservation with local economic opportunities;
- preparation of policy guidance and tutorials to support entrepreneurs entering biodiversity-friendly markets.

ANNEX A: ABRIDGED INTERVIEWS WITH R4L IMPLEMENTATION SITE BUSINESS STAKEHOLDERS

Country	Serbia
IS Name	Vlasina
Sector(s)	Tourism
Date	09/07/24
Format	In person
Activities of the business	Promotion and increase of tourism in region, which includes Vlasina protected area. Provision of facilities e.g. picnic areas, toilets etc. Coordinates with National Tourism Organisation in Belgrade – must send plans to them. Budget is 140m RSD, of which 30m is allocated to the nature park. They are also involved in tourism projects, e.g. Ministry of Tourism and IPRA with Bulgarian projects. Nearly all focus on Vlasina.
Date formed	2002
Employees	13
Business size	Small
Ownership	Public
Growth plans	Increase numbers of tourists at Vlasina through more facilities and promotion on social media. Potential for fishing (there is competition on catfish angling – can be 70 kg), water-based sports (there is a rowing regatta competition involving Bulgaria, North Macedonia), nature-based, biking, hiking, triathlon – Balkan championship. Currently about 100,000 visitors pa; a lot of passing tourists from Bulgaria and Greece, post-coast visits. The majority of visitors are Serbian. There is no aim to have mass tourism, just to support local population. Wants to increase infrastructure especially wastewater treatment, the lack of which is a blockage for investors. Would need €25m to have a system around the lake and there is a project for that – a 50 year aim. Started to purchase land for it, and it will have national finance. It will help to increase the water quality and attract investors in accommodations.
Main problems	Lack of staff: need at least 20 people to function properly. Lack of accommodation beds and camping sites. Do not collect occupancy data. Total beds are around 20,000 in the whole Vlasina area. It is expected to increase – more hotels are being constructed. Swimming in the lake is not permitted officially for safety reasons.
Environmental policy	No - national regulations apply
Knowledge of IS plan	Yes
Expected restoration benefits	Good for birdwatching tourism
Interviewee questions	Funding source and role of interviewer
Interviewer remarks	Potential to provide expertise for ecotourism development plan and site promotion as a destination

Country	Serbia
IS Name	Vlasina
Sector(s)	Energy
Date	10/07/24
Format	In person
Activities of the business	Production of electrical power
Date formed	1955
Employees	Not stated
Business size	Medium
Ownership	Public
Growth plans	Nothing in respect of the lake for the next few years
Main problems	Aquatic plants and peat plaurs block the channel outlets. Climate change is not a big concern (but they have no data).
Environmental policy	Yes – provided
Knowledge of IS plan	Received some information from R4L but unaware of specific site. On being shown the site on Google Earth they had no concerns with the plan.
Expected restoration benefits	Opportunity for benefits unclear but willing to collaborate.
Interviewee questions	None
Interviewer remarks	Opportunity to engage with project implementation (corporate sponsorship). Potential to advise on measures to stabilise eroding shorelines to prevent peat entering the lake - and reduce significant peat loss

Country	Slovakia
IS Name	Rudava
Sector(s)	Fisheries
Date	16/07/24
Format	In person
Activities of the business	Main activity is fish breeding / aquaculture of carp, pike, zander, catfish and others, chiefly for restocking but also some direct sales because breeding grounds have been affected e.g. by dams. Revenue comes from permits and fish stock sales.
Date formed	mid 1920s
Employees	Not stated
Business size	Medium
Ownership	NGO with over 130,000 members
Growth plans	The organisation has been growing for last 5 years (there was a peak during the COVID-19 period) and will likely stabilise soon
Main problems	Catastrophic reduction of some fish populations from dams, pollution, and invasive species in breeding areas (topmouth gudgeon <i>Pseudorasbora parva</i> , goldfish <i>Carassius auratus</i> , round goby <i>Neogobius melanostomus</i>). In addition silver carp <i>Hypophthalmichthys nobilis</i> is causing problems with in some Slovak rivers. Climate change is causing rising water temperatures that specially affect salmonids, small streams are drying up in summer.
Environmental policy	No - national regulations apply
Knowledge of IS plan	Yes
Expected restoration benefits	Rudava is one of the fishing grounds managed by the organisation, and is monitored internally using electrofishing. Interesting project for recording colonisation and succession of wild species in the restored stretch. No plan yet to carry out monitoring but could be a good place for the citizen science. A few locals have permits to angle there (it is a small river and not many big fish). Rules for keeping fish caught according to species and size, and no fishing in the spawning period, are set out in legislation. There are some private ponds nearby but not under the organisation's management. There is a problem of releasing exotic species from the ponds.
Interviewee questions	None
Interviewer remarks	Opportunity for local stakeholder participation in monitoring fish community development through a local angling group

Country	Slovakia
IS Name	Rudava
Sector(s)	Water management
Date	17/07/24
Format	In person
Activities of the business	Main role is maintaining water courses and infrastructure relating to flood control and irrigation. Gives licences for water abstraction and supply but wastewater treatment done by separate companies which are monitored by the organisation.
Date formed	1993 (formed from previous state organisations)
Employees	c. 3,000 with c. 100 in this branch
Business size	Large
Ownership	State company, supervised by Ministry of Environment
Web site	www.svp.sk
Growth plans	More staff and equipment needed to function better especially during flood events
Main problems	Flood control especially in the lower sections of the Rudava where the mouth is affected by Morava river water levels, while the upper sections can suffer from low flows. In some places, beaver dams keep water levels high in places and farmers complain but it is a protected species so consultation with the landscape park needed to see if the dam can be removed.
Environmental policy	There is a 10 year water plan (2016-2026) that focuses on flood protection (legally binding) and internal documents on approval of water management (supply and quality). There is a water protection zone 5m from the banks for water courses (can be 10m if important for water management) measured from the point from where water overtops the bank i.e. highest levels. The zone should be free of big trees or shrubs, buildings, fences or other obstructions.
Knowledge of IS plan	R4L has informed them and there is no problem with the proposal.
Expected restoration benefits	None identified
Interviewee questions	Still awaiting the technical specifications for the restoration proposal for review.
Interviewer remarks	The organisation is highly focused on engineered flood protection schemes. There could be an opportunity to influence the next water plan to introduce more NbS approaches. The positive role of beavers in water management could be highlighted.

Country	Slovakia
IS Name	Rudava
Sector(s)	Farming
Date	17/07/24
Format	In person
Activities of the business	2900 ha of farmland operated by several daughter companies involved in production of cereals, forage, oilseeds, legumes; beef livestock. Some organic production.
Date formed	1996, derived from former state farm
Employees	c. 60
Business size	Medium
Ownership	Private limited company
Growth plans	No plan to expand but keep current status (and avoid splitting to smaller units)
Main problems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Keeping / hiring qualified staff (salaries higher in Bratislava) > Subsidies are targeted on smaller farm units > Located in LFA because of soil quality and structure (light sands), erosion and high water level > Regulations under RDP / CAP are strong, part of it deals with invasive species (Solidago, Ambrosia, Polygonum, Fallopia, Robinia). Ambrosia competes with organic production especially as it is late flowering. Measures are taken to control with mulch but reintroduction from neighbouring areas. Set aside fallow under CAP facilitates Ambrosia. Dry periods impact grasslands, and wind erosion of slopes. Climate change is a coming problem, already visible (change of rainfall patterns are more irregular, episodic, although quantity stays the same).
Environmental policy	No formal policy as farming is already adapted to the local conditions and biodiversity protection. However, the company plans to cope with the stated problems by requesting the State Nature Conservancy to classify some grasslands as semi-natural e.g. hay meadows.
Knowledge of IS plan	Yes – but details explored in depth with R4L at the start of the meeting
Expected restoration benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Wetter areas can improve productivity but also encourages less useful species such as sedges > However, also anticipate problems with areas becoming too wet and so delaying harvests > Land is leased as grassland, so any permanent water would pose a problem > There may be a minor reputational benefit for doing something good for nature
Interviewee questions	Queries about details of the restoration project, and potential compensation for any land that gets flooded
Interviewer remarks	Opportunity to collaborate closely with the business and use as a model for other floodplain farmers.

Country	Austria
IS Name	March
Sector(s)	Farming, Forestry
Date	14/07/24
Format	In person
Activities of the business	The estate has of area of 6650 ha: 600 in arable production, 3200 forests, 100 meadows, and rest wetlands set asides. Owned by the family since the 12th century.
Date formed	2021, converted from a foundation
Employees	35 - 45
Business size	Small
Ownership	Foundation Prince Liechtenstein
Growth plans	No substantial plan for expansion – mainly improving internal business. There might be some opportunistic land purchases at the margins of the estate.
Main problems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Market for arable / timber products > Reduced CAP subsidies and regulations > Nature conservation laws are a challenge (area is a Natura 2000 site, Ramsar, protected landscape) and do not allow totally free management of the land > Climate change is a big concern concerning rainfall patterns and temperatures. Trying to adapt by growing more winter crops (better water availability) reducing conifers and planting more mixed woodland stands; retaining as much water as possible. > Invasive species are a problem with some plants and trees especially in wetland areas – Acer, Aster.
Environmental policy	No specific policy but the nature protection activities are led directly by the managing director and follows the published texts on the web site and information materials. There is close cooperation with NGOs e.g. ViaDuna, BirdLife International, WWF. However, always looking for compensation or contracts for setting aside land (forests mainly) for biodiversity. The estate is the only Austrian holder of a Wildlife Estates Certificate from the European Landowners' Organisation.
Knowledge of IS plan	Yes
Expected restoration benefits	Will improve habitat for fish, add more water in the wetlands and elevate the water table, more biodiversity. The company has rights for angling on March and Thaya rivers which is licensed to

	some 200 fishers (using the hanging nets – Daubel – or two rods) and produces a significant income. The restoration will provide more breeding / nursery grounds. Fishing seasons are regulated by legislation according to species. Carp (trying to increase numbers of wild variety from local supplier), catfish, pike, zander. Some invasive species arrive from the Danube – for example round goby <i>Neogobius melanostomus</i> kills local gudgeon <i>Gobius gobius</i> .
Interviewee questions	What are the next steps? R4L provides more information
Interviewer remarks	Possible opportunity to involve the estate in the development of European OECMs.

Country	Romania
IS Name	Enisala
Sector(s)	Farming
Date	23/07/24
Format	In person
Activities of the business	Cereal production, soya, corn, sunflower on 160 ha of leased land. Member of a consortium operating across c. 2000 ha.
Date formed	2009
Employees	2 (c. 40 in the consortium)
Business size	Micro
Ownership	Single private owner from Enisala
Growth plans	Originally took the site to have access to irrigation water, but now seeking to diversify and considering angling and agrotourism investments (seeking external funding).
Main problems	The irrigation system (overhead sprays fed by canals) has to be installed and maintained by themselves and is costly. They have an abstraction licence from Apele Romana, without a fixed limit but it can be imposed during drought periods. No serious problems with invasive species. They will adapt to climate change effects: they already see reduced productivity wherever there is no irrigation. The most vulnerable are spring-sown crops that now always suffer from low water levels. They may start growing crops requiring less water.
Environmental policy	Stated that the consortium has one.
Knowledge of IS plan	No. R4L introduced the restoration plan.
Expected restoration benefits	Could be beneficial for their agrotourism development.
Interviewee questions	None
Interviewer remarks	Opportunity to help develop agrotourism / angling (a similar operation is located near Histria) and adopting drought-prone farming practices.

Country	Romania
IS Name	Enisala
Sector(s)	Tourism
Date	23/07/24
Format	In person
Activities of the business	Tourism – 20 rooms, restaurant, boat trips on Razim, Zhurilovka, Murighiol (own boat for 6 people). Occupancy 30 to 50%, from May to October. Four one-week summer schools for 30 – 35 Romanian children are organised each year in July to learn English by acting (started 15 years ago). Three voluntary drama students from Cambridge will come to teach and an amphitheatre was constructed specially for the purpose, plus other activities.
Date formed	2000
Employees	10
Business size	Medium
Ownership	Single private owner, living in Bucharest
Growth plans	Expansion of the site to 13000 sq.m
Main problems	Very low numbers of tourists coming to this part of the delta. Other destinations preferred (Greece, Bulgaria, Turkey) perhaps because of the war in Ukraine.
Environmental policy	The owner may have one
Knowledge of IS plan	Yes
Expected restoration benefits	The restoration plan is very good – the owner had a fish farm business there previously. Would be good to improve water circulation, provide angling and irrigation water. It could bring more tourists to stay, or take tourists there e.g. for canoeing.
Interviewee questions	None
Interviewer remarks	Opportunity to develop water-based tourism activities, and good facilities for group activities - retreats, seminars, sports.

Country	Romania
IS Name	Enisala
Sector(s)	Tourism, Reed harvesting

Date	24/07/24
Format	Online
Activities of the business	Tourist accommodation in cottages and harvesting and export of reed thatch bundles to Germany (not processed – manually sorted and cleaned). They have a Seiga-type harvester and access to 200 ha of reedbed.
Date formed	2017
Employees	1 full time, 6 when needed
Business size	Micro
Ownership	One private owner living locally
Growth plans	Hopes to utilise the reed waste from making thatch bundles. Last year they had 30% waste, c. 40 tons.
Main problems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Lack of good workers > Timely issue of harvest permit by Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve Administration > Lack of overview of market to set their prices > Expanding market for export > Difficult to obtain loans because they have a low profit margin > Need to have storage facilities and better machines
Environmental policy	No
Knowledge of IS plan	Yes
Expected restoration benefits	Open to suggestions for cooperation but no direct benefit seen at present as they operate in Vadu which is quite far from Enisala.
Interviewee questions	Asked for details of reed markets and thatch prices. Referred to Greifswald University in Germany.
Interviewer remarks	Opportunity to develop reed harvesting operation at Enisala. Possibility to include in upcoming DDNI project on manufacture of reed briquettes, including study tour to Germany.

ANNEX B: ABRIDGED INTERVIEWS WITH R4L ASSOCIATED REGION SITE BUSINESS STAKEHOLDERS

Country	Armenia
AR Name	Armash fish ponds, Ararat
Sector(s)	Fish production
Date	06/06/2025
Format	In person
Activities of the business	Mainly production of various carp species: common, grass and bighead sold fresh (no market for smoked or salted) in local markets, occasionally to wholesalers and restaurants. The site is about 1500 ha. The pond banks are grazed by cattle belonging to local villagers free of charge. The ponds are drained on a rotation of 2 years fish, one year dry. Dry ponds are leased out chiefly for growing melons.
Date formed	1975
Employees	41
Business size	Small
Ownership	Private closed joint-stock company
Growth plans	No expansion of the fishery, but the company has recently built high quality accommodation for 16 people with the aim of lodging birdwatching groups. Hopes to develop rice production in some of the ponds to diversify crop production and also rice will attract waders and ducks.
Main problems	The main problems are - operational costs and taxes are high in relation to the value of the fish - neighbouring fish farms are smaller but not legally registered so do not pay taxes and thus sell their production for lower prices - water supply is mainly artesian and the government wants to reduce abstraction so some ponds are drying out as a result
Environmental policy	The company has installed solar panels to reduce energy costs
Knowledge of AR plan	The company owns the land and supports to restoration proposal as he likes nature. However, the grant is likely to be insufficient to meet the restoration costs and other funding sources will be required.
Expected restoration benefits	More nature (especially birds) on the site to attract birdwatchers.
Interviewee questions	Asked for technical support for rice growing in terms of machinery.
Interviewer remarks	Could put the company in touch with growers in southern Ukraine (Kilia), Spain and Italy.

Country	Armenia
AR Name	Armash fish ponds, Ararat
Sector(s)	Tourism
Date	05/06/2025
Format	In person
Activities of the business	Member of IATA. Mainly B2B: company groups and event management, but also bespoke special interest tours (cultural, adventure, hiking, nature). All guests are visitors arriving from Europe (Italy, France, Germany) so they have a multi-lingual staff. Covid impacted business in terms of significant loss of revenue as well as developing new and broader range of offers. They have a separate company that holds the local franchise for Hertz car rental.
Date formed	1997
Employees	10 (up to 49)
Business size	Small
Ownership	Private
Growth plans	They are hiring and training new staff as well as attending more tourism fairs abroad to recover after Covid. In 2019, before the pandemic, they had some 12,000 guests and 25 staff, in 2024 there were around 5,000 guests and 12 staff.
Main problems	Lack of regulation enforcement and licensing of operators. There are many unprofessional operators but they are rarely prosecuted, so they undercut prices (they lost about 50 parties to a Georgia-based agent in 2024 who established a local company for \$10 and bought a local vehicle).
Environmental policy	Applying for certification with Travel4Life. They provide flagons of water on tours to refill plastic bottles, collect waste for recycling and use paper cups and plates.
Knowledge of AR plan	The company runs a tour to Armash (one day only) but is not really aware of the restoration project.
Expected restoration benefits	Could allow more tours to be run to the fish ponds for birdwatchers.
Interviewee questions	What advice on tourism fairs
Interviewer remarks	Suggested attendance of the Global Bird Fair in England (at first as visitor and then to have a stall there)

Country	Armenia
AR Name	Armash fish ponds, Ararat
Sector(s)	Tourism
Date	05/06/2025
Format	In person
Activities of the business	Mostly cultural tourism (wine, pilgrims), hiking, birding, archaeology, bespoke tours. Guests largely from Italy and France, usually in groups from 20 to 40 people. Armash rarely visited and then just for one day.
Date formed	1996
Employees	9
Business size	Micro
Ownership	Private
Growth plans	A slow increase in business, hoping to recover after big impact from Covid - previously employed 16 staff but now only 9. Before Covid, catered for some 3000 guests per year, but in 2024 there were only 880 visitors.
Main problems	The main problems are <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - difficult to recruit staff with languages and guiding skills (especially for hiking and birding) because local training is not at a high level and students prefer the IT and financial sectors - infrastructure has improved a lot (there are more restaurants and toilet facilities in the rural areas) but still not sufficient - government is introducing a licensing scheme but criteria and enforcement uncertain - littering is an issue at tourist sites - local political conditions remain unstable
Environmental policy	The company tends to use LPG fuel in vehicles, and reduces use of plastic water bottles by refilling them from a flagon.
Knowledge of AR plan	Not aware of the wetland restoration plan. Armash is known for birdwatching only, no other attractions there.
Expected restoration benefits	None.
Interviewee questions	None.
Interviewer remarks	None.

Country	Armenia
AR Name	Armash fish ponds, Ararat
Sector(s)	Tourism
Date	05/06/2025
Format	In person
Activities of the business	Mainly B2B: company groups and event management. All guests are incoming visitors arriving from Europe (Italy, France, Germany, Poland, Netherlands and some Russians). Normal group size is 15 - 20 people, with a maximum of 35, aged from 40s to 70s.
Date formed	1996
Employees	Not stated
Business size	Medium
Ownership	Private
Growth plans	There was large impact on the company from Covid, but staff were retained and business is gradually recovering. Obtaining licenses for businesses and guides has become easier since 2018, and has eliminated corruption. They are redesigning tours to combine themes such as culture with birding and meeting a demand to cater for smaller groups, and there are schemes to support development of guest houses.
Main problems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National and international political issues (relations with Azerbaijan, Ukraine, sanctions on Russia) means Armenia has proximity to dangerous areas that deters visitors. - Flights to Yerevan are costly and only a few are direct. - There is a lack of rural infrastructure and facilities. - It is difficult to make accommodations sustainable.
Environmental policy	The company tries to reduce use of plastics, using flagons to refill bottles, and cleans up litter from picnic sites and hiking routes. They encourage guest houses to install solar water heating and energy.
Knowledge of AR plan	Not aware of the restoration plan.
Expected restoration benefits	Would be good if a guest house and visitor centre are part of the project.
Interviewee questions	None.
Interviewer remarks	None

Country	Armenia
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AR Name	Armash fish ponds, Ararat
Sector(s)	Tourism
Date	05/06/2025
Format	In person
Activities of the business	Organising tours in nature for small private groups of 10 - 12 people (mainly hiking). Uses local accommodation to ensure authenticity. Francophone, working with agencies in France and Belgium.
Date formed	2014
Employees	Not stated
Business size	Micro
Ownership	Private
Growth plans	The company expects the tourism sector in Armenia to grow quickly following a big decline during Covid and once conflicts in the region have subsided. Accordingly, although company prefers to stay small, it could become very large.
Main problems	The main problems are: - making business forecasts is presently very difficult because of the uncertain situation of the country - the lack of infrastructure and facilities limits routes for hiking tours (these are normally 8 - 10 km/day over 10 to 12 days and the guests are younger).
Environmental policy	Environmental measures are largely driven by the demands of the guests for example no plastic water bottles and recycling waste.
Knowledge of AR plan	The company is aware of the Armash fish ponds and sometimes arranges visits for birdwatchers.
Expected restoration benefits	The main benefit would be increased revenue from more visitors going to the site.
Interviewee questions	Is the project actually feasible? For tourism there must be provision for a shady picnic area, sign and information boards, ecotoilets and skilled guides.
Interviewer remarks	Comments noted

Country	Belgium
AR Name	Grote Meers
Sector(s)	Water management
Date	19/06/2025
Format	In person
Activities of the business	Wastewater treatment: collecting household wastewater from municipal sewers in collector sewers, transporting it to wastewater treatment plants, where it is treated in accordance with EU and Flemish standards. Over 100 municipalities are customers
Date formed	1990
Employees	ca. 1300
Business size	Large
Ownership	Public. Profits used to improve efficiency and develop new operations.
Growth plans	There will be modest growth, looking for new business opportunities and innovations to increase revenue (e.g. heat exchangers in sewers to transfer warmth to homes), and do more socially responsible activities.
Main problems	Highly distributed management / decision making – lots of actors and no central coordination which would improve effectiveness Cost of infrastructure maintenance and renovations Finding technical staff Relations with RBM managers seeking concrete solutions
Environmental policy	Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD). Green Finance Report: https://www.aquafin.be/sites/aquafin/files/2025-04/GFF%20report%202024_0.pdf
Knowledge of AR plan	Brief given but no deep involvement.
Expected restoration benefits	Could benefit if rules permitted involvement, but presently have to do all works within other specific sites.
Interviewee questions	None
Interviewer remarks	None

Country	Belgium
AR Name	Grote Meers
Sector(s)	Water management
Date	16/06/2025
Format	In person
Activities of the business	Dredging solutions, offshore energy, construction projects.
Date formed	1938
Employees	ca. 9000
Business size	Large

Ownership	Private - Family with equity
Growth plans	Growth is going slower than expected for coastal works, but working on land reinstatement and developing low emission vessels is expanding.
Main problems	Local authority regulations are often not in accordance with national / international requirements The impact of the Russian invasion of Ukraine is making financial planning uncertain
Environmental policy	Joined the Science-Based Target Initiative, with the company's targets validated in 2023. https://www.jandenul.com/our-sustainability-performance
Knowledge of AR plan	The company is aware of the plan as it regularly collaborates with the local Natuurpunt division (Natuurpunt Aalst) for e.g. groundworks, lending a crane to reach stork nests for ringing young.
Expected restoration benefits	The project is small but the company expects to gain some reputational benefits (mainly among its own staff some of whom are volunteers at the site).
Interviewee questions	None
Interviewer remarks	None

Country	Portugal
AR Name	Lagoas de Bertandos e São Pedro d'Arcos
Sector(s)	Tourism
Date	08/05/2025
Format	In Person
Activities of the business	Provision of accommodation (12 refurbished local houses) at Cerquido village in nearby mountains (Serra de Arga), guided horse trekking
Date formed	2012
Employees	Not specified
Business size	Micro
Ownership	Private, single owner
Growth plans	Expanding horse riding offer, opening a small café and food store in Cerquido village
Main problems	Remote location of the cabins means all employees have to be local and few are available The company has received some support from EU Structural Funds
Environmental policy	High respect for heritage and sustainable practices
Knowledge of AR plan	Aware of the project and funding but not the details
Expected restoration benefits	Has seen a lot of improvements at the landscape park with improved offers for visitors. The restoration could increase the local tourism sector.
Interviewee questions	Asked about the importance of the site
Interviewer remarks	Informed about its strengths (important habitats, strong emphasis on education and public awareness) and weaknesses (invasive species in the forests, and lack on interpretation on the trails)

Country	Portugal
AR Name	Lagoas de Bertandos e São Pedro d'Arcos
Sector(s)	Tourism
Date	09/05/2025
Format	In Person
Activities of the business	Adventure tourism company (tree trail, climbing, zip wire, paint ball, biking, orienteering and hiking trails) that operates on leased municipal land within the reserve. The company serves several thousand clients a year with a turnover of about €350,000.
Date formed	2007
Employees	Not stated
Business size	Micro
Ownership	Limited liability company
Growth plans	The owner hoped to attract more foreign tourists to increase revenue.
Main problems	Seasonality of activities, concentrated in the summer holidays
Environmental policy	The company implements the following practices: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Setting routes that avoid sensitive areas, such as bird breeding sites or fragile habitats; - We check and encourage customers not to dispose of garbage in the water or other places; - We organise a tour to clean and collect plastics that enter water courses; - We buy our equipment from suppliers committed to responsible environmental practices; - We carefully use our equipment to increase its durability and good condition; - We do not use toxic cleaning products on equipment that can contaminate the water; - We communicate information about local biodiversity and how to protect it during tours; - We encourage participants to value and act sustainably in nature.
Knowledge of AR plan	Knows about the restoration plan

Expected restoration benefits	We maintain valid BIOSPHERA accreditation, recognition of sustainable development. To communicate and present to our customers the need to protect ecosystem, enhancing the value of the territory in environmental and tourist terms.
Interviewee questions	None
Interviewer remarks	None

Country	Portugal
AR Name	Lagoas de Bertandos e São Pedro d'Arcos
Sector(s)	Agriculture
Date	09/05/2025
Format	In Person
Activities of the business	Production of organic beef from local breed Minhota livestock. The cattle graze in the reserve's meadows which were formerly cereal fields before being reseeded with a flower-rich seed mix but dominated by clovers and palatable grasses.
Date formed	2008
Employees	Not stated
Business size	Micro
Ownership	Private company, 50 / 50 ownership
Growth plans	The owners have only just gone organic and have taken a big loan to put in fencing, reseeded and animal maintenance. So far, sales are mostly at non-organic rates but they hope to get premium prices over time and would like to expand the number of livestock and area grazed.
Main problems	Small size plots, and costs and difficulty of placing fences around the perimeters of grazing areas
Environmental policy	They hope to obtain organic production certification.
Knowledge of AR plan	Just superficial knowledge.
Expected restoration benefits	The benefit can be mutual, if we identify areas that are useful for grazing and making the perimeter fence infrastructure makes it feasible for us to place enough grazing animals to create positive impacts on the ecosystem.
Interviewee questions	None
Interviewer remarks	None

Country	Sweden
AR Name	Svensksundsviken
Sector(s)	Agriculture
Date	26/05/2025
Format	In Person
Activities of the business	Vikbo lands Struts & Meat breeds ostriches and cattle for meat production, with its own farm shop, slaughterhouse for wild game, and restaurant. The farm currently has over 100 ostriches (slaughtering 130 - 150 birds / year) and 35 breeding cows and own 30 ha of land for fodder production. They receive many visitors to see the ostriches, who also form the main market for sales (80%) compared with external local sales (20%). The farm shop also sells various ostrich-derived products and souvenirs such as feather dusters, egg-shade lamps, fresh and cured meat, soaps and cosmetics, and soft toys.
Date formed	1997
Employees	Not stated
Business size	Micro
Ownership	Private, family business
Growth plans	Business is doing well at present. The company is building a new animal shed for expansion, and plans to build another in due course.
Main problems	The main problems are - regulations which are not easily applicable for ostrich farming - potential impact of climate change that could lower groundwater levels and cause droughts
Environmental policy	The farm produces electricity from solar panels and in 2019 installed a log-based biofuel boiler generating 98kWh for heating and hot water.
Knowledge of AR plan	Only recently became aware of the restoration project. Although the farm lies in the catchment area, there is no direct involvement.
Expected restoration benefits	Might have some benefits in future but these remain unclear.
Interviewee questions	None.
Interviewer remarks	None

Country	Sweden
AR Name	Svensksundsviken
Sector(s)	Agriculture

Date	26/05/2025
Format	In Person
Activities of the business	Purely arable farm of 470 ha, growing winter wheat, rape, peas, linseed. A separate activity is freight haulage and undertaking local mechanical works - snow ploughing, ditch maintenance, forestry and other ground works.
Date formed	Farm originally set up in 1947 with the present company formed in 1991.
Employees	None
Business size	None
Ownership	Micro
Growth plans	The activities are quite stable, but admitted that their business model depended on CAP subsidies although they claimed they could do without if there was a phasing out coupled with lower land prices and higher cereal prices.
Main problems	The main problems mentioned were - regulations controlling the use of pesticides such as Nexide (gamma-cyhalothrin, a broad-spectrum pyrethroid insecticide that is especially toxic for honeybees) - increasing frequency of extreme weather events, especially rainfall
Environmental policy	They strive for maximum efficiency - no nature compromises or even renewable energy features. However, cereal straw is ploughed back (reduced till) and a new high efficiency grain drying facility has eliminated the need for oil
Knowledge of AR plan	The owner was aware of the plan since one of the streams (Vadsbäcken) crossed his land.
Expected restoration benefits	The owner was sceptical of the success of the rather modest restoration project but ready to accept it providing there is no risk of flooding. Perhaps it could provide some water storage for irrigation purposes.
Interviewee questions	None
Interviewer remarks	None

Country	Ukraine
AR Name	Bilohorshcha
Sector(s)	Food processing
Date	24/06/2025
Format	In person
Activities of the business	Meat processing (pork, beef, chicken) for dry sausage (kolbasa) and fresh meat. Sold only in Ukraine, no exports. The land is adjacent to the restoration site and is owned by the company and equipment imported from Germany.
Date formed	2020
Employees	Not stated
Business size	Small
Ownership	Private, family business
Growth plans	Has some ideas for expansion but future uncertain and more investors would be needed.
Main problems	The company has only recently started to operate but work is constrained by Russian invasion and difficulty of employing more staff.
Environmental policy	Solar panels are to be installed (300 kW power) and all waste is incinerated.
Knowledge of AR plan	Not aware of the plan until now.
Expected restoration benefits	The Director welcomed the restoration plan as he liked nature (and had a good view of the site from his office window). He would be happy to provide support although he did not think he would have any economic benefits.
Interviewee questions	What was the purpose of the visit.
Interviewer remarks	To inform stakeholders about the restoration plan and explore potential benefits for local businesses.

**ANNEX C: FISH SPAWNING GROUND AT FOKUROPUSZTA, HUNGARY
(R4L Monitoring Site 7)**

**COST-BENEFIT ANALYSIS OF THE FOKORÚPUSZTA
FISH SPAWNING SITE UNDER THE RESTORE4LIFE
PROJECT**

REKK
July 2025

Restore4Life

RESTORING WETLANDS
FOR A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE

GRANT AGREEMENT NO.: 101112736
CALL: HORIZON-MISS-2022-OCEAN-01
TOPIC: HORIZON-MISS-2022-OCEAN-01-02
TYPE OF ACTION: HORIZON INNOVATION ACTIONS

Work package	4
Task	4.3
Due date	31/07/25
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Deliverable lead	KOTIVIZIG
Authors	Gábor Horváth, András Kis, Attila Lovas, Gábor Ungvári
Reviewers	György Rátfai, Paul Goriup, Martin Pusch
Abstract	<p>This study, conducted under the Horizon Europe Restore4Life project, evaluates the economic and ecological feasibility of operating natural floodplain spawning grounds for fishery management along the Middle Tisza River, focusing on the Fokorúpuszta site. Building on previous findings from the Interreg Danube Floodplain project, it provides a detailed financial analysis, institutional recommendations, and operational guidelines. The research shows that natural reproduction at the spawning ground can be significantly more cost-effective than artificial fish stocking, even with infrequent success. While Hungarian law still mandates annual stocking, natural spawning could reduce supplemental costs. The study highlights the ecological value of floodplain habitats, which support biodiversity, flood mitigation, and local climate regulation. It recommends formalising a cooperation agreement among key stakeholders to ensure long-term, cost-efficient site operation. The findings support redirecting some fishery funds toward spawning ground management and emphasise the importance of</p>

	monitoring, stakeholder collaboration, and adaptive management strategies for successful implementation and conservation outcomes.
Keywords	Nature-based business, economic benefits from wetland restoration, inland fisheries

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Nature of the deliverable: PU

Report

Dissemination Level

PU Public, fully open, e.g. web

CL Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

CO Confidential to R4L project and Commission Services

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1 Executive Summary

This analysis, carried out under the Horizon Europe Restore4Life project, explores how natural floodplain spawning grounds can be integrated into fishery management along the Middle Tisza River, and how the operation of ecosystem services in the floodplain can become economically self-sustaining over the long term. The study primarily assessed the economic feasibility of operating the Fokorúpuszta spawning ground, while also aiming to support the establishment of a cooperation agreement among the relevant regional stakeholders. It is based on the widely accepted and repeatedly confirmed assumption that economic sustainability is a prerequisite for environmental sustainability. If a conservation-focused intervention is not financially viable, its long-term functionality is likely to be compromised. Therefore, it is essential to assess whether the operation of spawning grounds is economically justified.

The present work builds on an earlier study conducted in 2020 under the Interreg Danube Transnational Project titled *Danube Floodplain*. That project comprehensively assessed the costs and benefits of expanding the floodplain in the Fokorúpuszta area, upstream of Szolnok. The findings confirmed that the dike relocation represented a socially beneficial investment. The study also briefly addressed the economic rationale for operating the newly created spawning ground, which emerged as an attractive alternative. The current project goes further, examining in detail the financial framework required for operating the spawning ground and identifying the institutional, legal and organisational prerequisites for its successful launch and long-term operation.

In addition to Fokorúpuszta, three other spawning grounds exist in the vicinity of Szolnok. The experiences related to these sites were also integrated into the analysis. Although the recent operational experiences vary, they collectively underscore the ecological and fishery-related importance of floodplain habitats. It is clear that the success of fishery utilisation depends heavily on the timing of water levels, meteorological conditions, infrastructure readiness, and the alignment of conservation and fishery objectives – as well as the ability to respond rapidly to changing natural conditions.

Based on our calculations, the annual operating cost of the Fokorúpuszta spawning ground is estimated at 85,000 to 130,000 HUF per hectare. One hectare of spawning ground can, on average, generate natural reproduction equivalent to ten hectares of natural river surface. Therefore, following a successful spawning event, the annual replenishment cost per hectare of river surface is around 8,500–13,000 HUF. In contrast, according to KÖTIHESZ data, the annual cost of stocking purchased juvenile fish ranges from 41,000 to 52,000 HUF per hectare. If spawning were successful every year at the Fokorúpuszta site, the operation of the spawning ground would be clearly advantageous from an economic perspective. While ideal conditions are unlikely to occur annually, even if successful spawning occurs once every 3–5 years, the natural reproduction remains more cost-effective - or at least competitive - compared to artificial stocking. Our calculations are based on conservative assumptions; even with success every 10 years, operating the site may still be worthwhile, though greater certainty applies to the 3–5-year interval scenario.

Current Hungarian regulations do not allow natural spawning grounds to completely replace artificial stocking, as the law mandates a minimum annual stocking requirement. However, successful natural reproduction can partially offset the need for stocking beyond the minimum. Consequently, it is advisable to reallocate a portion of available funding for supplementary

stocking toward the operation of spawning grounds, as this investment is likely to yield returns over time.

Importantly, the above conclusions are valid only if the initial investment cost is not borne by the anglers' association, as the opportunity to establish a semi-natural spawning habitat arose from a floodplain realignment project primarily funded for flood mitigation, not for fish spawning. While operating the existing habitat is economically viable, there is no strong business case for developing new sites from private funds. However the multi-benefits of such a site make it a very likely candidate for getting restoration funds.

Beyond direct benefits to angling, several additional positive impacts - though not quantified in monetary terms - are clearly significant from both environmental and societal perspectives. Spawning grounds can contribute to flood risk reduction, thanks to the low surface roughness of the floodplain. Moreover, these habitats are vital not only for fish but also for various aquatic and semi-aquatic species, such as amphibians and waterbirds. Grazing in the area can further enhance ecological value, as manure supports plankton growth, providing essential food for fish larvae. The habitat also improves water retention in the area, helping to stabilise the local microclimate.

In order to implement the concept of operating spawning grounds and clarify roles and responsibilities among stakeholders, it is recommended that a formal agreement be concluded between KÖTIVIZIG and MOHOSZ (or KÖTIHESZ) as soon as possible. This would allow upcoming flood events to be utilised more effectively in support of fish reproduction. Based on the example of Doba, it would be reasonable to grant the angling association free access to manage the site.

The optimal mode of operation for the spawning ground has not yet been finalised. Clarifying certain key issues in advance - such as introducing mature breeding pairs of fish, removing invasive species, or supporting native species through improvements in riverbed morphology - can facilitate more effective management. Regular and targeted monitoring is essential, particularly regarding the composition of juvenile fish populations and the ecological status of surrounding water bodies. Conservation-focused monitoring should also be an integral component of any operational agreement.

The supportive attitude of the stakeholders involved with the spawning ground greatly facilitated the study. We hope this material will contribute to establishing a formal agreement for its institutionalised management. Special thanks are due to the regional angling association (KÖTIHESZ) and Béla Horváth for their contributions, as well as to the national park (HNPI) staff for their constructive input.

2 Introduction

This analysis was conducted within the framework of the Restore4Life Horizon Europe programme. The objective of Work Package 4 - in which the project partners collaborated on the case study - was to promote nature-based business solutions derived from restored wetlands. The Fokorúpuszta spawning ground was examined under Task 4.3, which aimed to identify the enabling conditions for embedding restored wetlands into the local economy.

The work builds upon a cost-benefit analysis (CBA) conducted under the Danube Floodplain Interreg programme, which included the valuation of ecosystem services and assessed the economic potential of the spawning ground created following dike relocation (see Chapter 3). Despite the promising potential, legal and institutional uncertainties hindered its full utilisation. The Restore4Life project therefore aimed to develop a viable financial model that reflects the interests of stakeholders responsible for managing the site.

The current analysis (Chapter 4) confirms the economic viability of operating the spawning ground (Chapter 5). In addition, discussions and consultations with stakeholders revealed that in order to realise the identified potential, it is essential to institutionalise the already initiated activities—making them regular and scheduled, embedding stakeholder interactions within a coordinated framework, and ensuring consistency in operations.

Under the proposed framework, the operation of floodplain spawning grounds could become an economically self-sustaining activity, providing a foundation for further ecosystem service-based value creation. We believe the research objectives are best served by supporting this institutionalisation process. This document is intended to serve as a basis for developing a long-term cooperation agreement among stakeholders. It clarifies the legal context for operating spawning grounds, identifies key economic considerations, explores common and individual interests, and makes recommendations for the content of the agreement (Chapter 6). We believe this material can provide a solid foundation for the negotiation process and the eventual drafting of the agreement.

The work carried out under the Restore4Life project is expected to have relevance beyond the local level. The insights and proposed modelling approaches could support the value-based integration of natural aquatic habitats into national fisheries, water management, and conservation practices. The model's applicability could also be explored in other floodplain spawning grounds, thereby contributing to the evolution of Hungary's national ecosystem services valuation framework and the economic validation of nature-based solutions - fully aligned with the objectives of the EU Green Deal and Biodiversity Strategy.

3 Summary of Previous Findings from the Danube Floodplain Project

This work builds upon a previous study carried out under the Interreg Danube Transnational Programme titled “Reducing the flood risk by examining the restoration of flood plains in the Danube river basin”. That study comprehensively evaluated the costs and benefits of expanding the floodplain in the Fokorúpuszta area, located upstream of Szolnok. The results were presented in a series of reports and published in both Hungarian and English. This chapter provides a brief summary of those findings, which form the basis for the current work.

3.1 Cost-Benefit Assessment of the Dike Relocation

The Fokorúpuszta site is located approximately 10 kilometres north of Szolnok, on the right bank of the river opposite Tiszapüspöki. The dike relocation was prompted by the construction of the motorway bypassing the city. The intervention aimed to give the river more space, but also changed the land use potential in the area. The total cost of the relocation, including related investments, amounted to several billion forints. The central question was whether the floodplain expansion represented a net benefit to society. To answer this, we used an extended cost-benefit analysis approach. In addition to calculating the net balance, we assessed how different stakeholder groups were affected—since a project can have a positive net benefit overall while still adversely impacting some affected parties.

The table below summarises the monetised elements (adjusted to current prices using inflation-corrected 2020 data). We calculated the present value of costs and benefits over a 50-year period using a 2% real discount rate. Overall, the benefits exceeded the costs by approximately HUF 1.7 billion, and the non-monetised benefits also outweighed the non-monetised costs. At a 1% discount rate, the surplus would rise to HUF 4 billion; at a 3% rate, it would fall to just HUF 30 million. Since the cost-benefit relationship is evaluated over a long time horizon, the results are highly sensitive to the discount rate applied.

Table 1 The present value of the costs and benefits of the Fokorúpuszta dike relocation (in million HUF)

Costs		Benefits	
Initial investment costs	-7,750	Reduced flood risk	8,843
Maintenance of meadows	-260	Fish spawning site	456
		Enhanced CO ₂ sequestration	380
		Other monetised benefits	29
Total	-8,010	Total	9,708

The initial investment costs totalled HUF 7.7 billion. The largest components were dike construction (HUF 3.2 billion), the rehabilitation of the borrow pit used for construction and the creation of the spawning ground on its site (HUF 1.1 billion), the relocation of high-voltage transmission lines crossing the river (HUF 0.9 billion), and the purchase of land newly incorporated into the floodplain (HUF 0.82 billion).

Among the benefits, flood risk reduction stands out by far. With a broader floodplain, water can disperse more evenly, which reduces the peak of flood waves downstream. This not only lowers the risk of dike breaches but also decreases the resources required for emergency response. The

average annualised value of this flood protection benefit is estimated at HUF 276 million per year - representing the long-term average gain in flood defence provided by the project. Approximately half of this annualised value relates to flood events with a return period between 30 and 100 years, while the other half corresponds to rarer, 100-year or greater flood events.

Other monetised land use benefits identified in the area fall into a lower utility category. This difference can largely be attributed to the specific location: the Fokorúpuszta site lies upstream of a medium-sized town, and any inundation there would result in substantial damages. Were this not the case—and if the site offered less in terms of flood risk reduction—then local, on-site benefits would have played a greater role in the overall balance. In light of these results, it becomes particularly important to assess whether there are enabling or limiting factors specific to certain uses. (For example, since the original study, leasing out pasture land has become possible, which has effectively neutralised the site's maintenance costs.) As will become apparent, the spawning ground is also a case that fits within this broader question.

In addition to monetised benefits, there are several other uses we did not attempt to quantify due to data limitations or methodological challenges, though their realisation would further improve the project's welfare impact. These include the expansion of beekeeping, hunting, nature tourism and other recreational or hobby activities. The intervention also contributes to the creation of a more resilient natural area — one that is more resistant to external pressures and potentially hosts greater biodiversity. It helps reduce pollutant loads in the environment and, even if only slightly, increases both infiltration into the groundwater and the water available for evaporation during periods of extended inundation.

3.2 Results Related to the Spawning Ground

In the 2020 Danube Floodplain study, the spawning ground was assessed as an integral component of fishery management along the relevant river stretch. We assumed that newly established and maintained spawning grounds could partially or fully substitute the annual stocking activities carried out by the area's fishery management organisation. Stocking is required to replenish the fish caught by anglers, and it is typically sourced from fish farms, which entails a clear financial cost. Operating natural spawning grounds can reduce this cost. In this context, the benefit of natural reproduction—considered an ecosystem service—can be interpreted as a form of cost saving.

Based on our earlier analysis, we estimated that the proposed spawning ground could reduce the annual costs associated with maintaining the fish population by approximately HUF 23.5 million. Naturally, the managing organisation would still need to cover the operational costs of maintaining the spawning ground itself, which brought the estimated net annual saving down to around HUF 18.9 million. However, it is important to note that this cost saving can only be realised in years when the river's water level is sufficiently high for the spawning ground to remain inundated for several days. In contrast, the maintenance costs of the spawning ground arise every year. Historical data from the 20 years preceding the study showed that such favourable water levels occurred in 80% of the years. Accordingly, the expected annual saving must be adjusted: $23.5 \text{ million HUF} \times 0.8 = 18.8 \text{ million HUF}$. Thus, under average conditions, we estimate the annual cost reduction to be approximately HUF 18.8 million.

Due to data limitations, our estimate only considered the restocking costs of common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) and did not account for other fish species. However, it should be emphasised

that the spawning ground also supports the reproduction of several other species, providing additional benefits—particularly for anglers and the ecosystem—which are difficult to quantify in monetary terms. As such, our cost-saving estimate should be regarded as conservative, representing a lower-bound scenario.

During the presentation of these findings, we received feedback indicating that several legal and practical administrative barriers prevent fishery managers from viewing natural spawning grounds as viable management tools. This insight was one of the key motivations behind launching the present, more detailed analysis.

4 The Role of Spawning Grounds in Fishery Management along the Middle Tisza

Interventions that have altered the living connection between the river and its floodplain have had a major impact on the potential for natural fish reproduction. This is particularly true for the Tisza River, where nineteenth-century river regulation significantly reduced the extent of the active floodplain. As a result, the current geomorphological features of the floodplain — such as oxbow lakes and shallow depressions — have gained increasing importance for spawning and fish recruitment. Their intentional use (through controlled water management) is not only crucial for supporting fish populations but also for mitigating the impacts of environmental crises. For instance, following the cyanide pollution incident of 2000, fish population recovery was supported by releasing young fish from floodplain borrow pits, oxbows, and the protected areas of the Tisza Lake, which had been temporarily isolated by sluice structures and later reopened.

The physical characteristics of the floodplain — oxbow lakes, shallow depressions, borrow pits, etc. — play an indispensable role in sustaining natural fish reproduction. However, this function is increasingly threatened over the long term by the shortening duration of water levels sufficient to inundate these areas. This is due in part to the deepening of the riverbed (meaning that the same low or medium flows now pass at a lower elevation relative to the terrain), and in part to unfavourable changes in hydrological patterns resulting from climate change. These trends underscore the need for much more deliberate water management — taking advantage of natural hydrological variability to recharge suitable areas, ensure water supply, and time water releases in a way that maximises reproductive success. Achieving this requires the presence of a capable and proactive management entity.

In Hungary, Act CII of 2013 on Fisheries and the Protection of Fish is the principal legal framework governing the maintenance of natural waters for recreational fishing / angling purposes. The law assigns the utilisation of natural waters primarily to recreational fishing activities. Within this framework, fisheries management is typically carried out by angling associations and their regional federations. In addition to supporting recreation, the fishery manager is also obliged to fulfil the legally defined objective of “preserving the fish populations of natural aquatic ecosystems”. The management of existing and potential floodplain spawning grounds is thus framed by two aims: compensating for angling-induced stock depletion and preserving natural populations. One of the key aims of this study is to explore whether these objectives are mutually reinforcing. A central question is whether the operation of natural spawning grounds offers measurable economic added value to fishery managers.

In the study area, fishery management is carried out by KÖTIHESZ (Federation of Angling Associations of the Middle Tisza Region). As a sub-lessee of the Hungarian National Anglers' Association (MOHOSZ), it holds fishing rights over 3,148 hectares of water bodies, including the entire section of the Tisza River within Jász-Nagykun-Szolnok and Bács-Kiskun counties, as well as the Nagykunság Main Canal and several smaller irrigation channels. In addition to the fishery manager, the operation of the spawning grounds also involves the regional water authority (KÖTIVIZIG) and the national park directorate (HNPI), both of which play significant roles. Post-flood fish rescue operations are conducted jointly by KÖTIVIZIG and KÖTIHESZ through coordinated efforts.

4.1 The Importance of Spawning Grounds in Stock Replenishment

4.1.1 Legal Framework

Act CII of 2013 on Fisheries and the Protection of Fish sets out the obligations of organisations with the right to manage fisheries in a given area regarding the maintenance of fish stocks. According to Section 48 of the Act, “in order to ensure the renewal of fish stocks and their habitats, the fishery manager is obliged to engage in annual restocking with species characteristic of the habitat, and to manage the area in a way that ensures the sustained presence of a fish population of appropriate age and size.” This activity must be carried out within the framework of a fishery management plan, as prescribed in Section 49 of the Act. Fishery managers are required to prepare a five-year management plan, which must be approved by the competent fisheries authority.

Section 49 of the Act outlines the required contents of such a plan. The detailed regulation of fishery activities is set out in Decree 133/2013 (XII. 29.) of the Ministry of Rural Development, which specifies, among other things, the structure of the management plan and the requirements related to restocking. Based on Section 49 of the Act, the management plan must include, among others:

- *(d) data on the planned minimum annual quantity of fish to be stocked, broken down by species and age group;*
- *(e) measures to protect water quality and fish stocks, including feeding and supplementary feeding;*
- *(f) actions to maintain aquatic vegetation and animal populations, as well as plans to designate fish refuge zones;*
- *(g) an action plan for the control of invasive, non-native fish species.*

Under the current Hungarian legal framework, it is clear that natural spawning grounds cannot fully replace stocking, as the law specifies a minimum annual restocking requirement for each fishery area (Section 49/d). In practice, the main challenge in relying on spawning grounds lies in the unpredictable, stochastic nature of their productivity — it is impossible to forecast how successful natural reproduction will be in a given year. However, the effective operation of spawning grounds may reduce the need for restocking beyond the mandatory minimum. Furthermore, spawning grounds can play a role in meeting several other requirements set out in the management plan. In particular, points (e), (f), and (g) of Section 49 highlight areas where measures to support native fish species through spawning grounds may be relevant.

Such activities can be defined and substantiated through bilateral or multilateral agreements between the fishery manager, the floodplain land manager (typically the regional water authority), and the national park. These agreements can help ensure predictable and well-coordinated maintenance of the spawning grounds (as discussed in Chapter 6).

Establishing and operating spawning grounds can support the protection and maintenance of fish populations, and may also contribute to the preservation of aquatic plants and animals. If natural spawning is successful and proper selection methods are applied, such sites can also assist in controlling invasive, non-native fish species.

4.1.2 Fish Stocking and Angling Statistics

Based on the annual reports of KÖTIHESZ, we examined the trends in fish stocking and angling statistics over the past years to get a more accurate picture of the required stocking quantities in the area, as well as the amount of fish caught by anglers. During the study, we focused on the section of the Tisza river belonging to KÖTIHESZ (403-258 river kilometers), as these values are more representative in terms of fish spawning areas compared to the aggregated data of all water bodies under KÖTIHESZ. The following figure presents the catch data for the most important fish species in terms of ticket sales and stocking.

Figure 1 Fishing license sales and catch data on the Tisza

Source: KÖTIHESZ annual reports

Based on the catch data, anglers caught approximately 30,000 kg of fish (carp, catfish, perch, and bream) between 2016 and 2018. This figure dramatically increased to 45,000 kg/year in 2019, and remained at this level until 2023. Over the entire period, an increase in the number of anglers can also be observed. In 2016, there were approximately 20,000 registered anglers in the associations belonging to KÖTIHESZ, and this number grew to nearly 30,000 by 2020, after which it either stagnated or slightly decreased in the following years. There was a slight decrease in annual area tickets, while daily tickets saw a slight increase. Based on this, there is no close correlation between the amount of fish caught, the number of anglers, and the trend in ticket sales. The reported catch quantity is influenced by many other factors.

The following figure shows the relationship between stocking and catch data from 2020 to 2023.

Figure 2 Fish stocking and catch data on the Tisza

Source: KÖTIHESZ annual reports

The actual stocking data ranged from 52,000 kg/year to 112,000 kg/year, with the 2020 stocking figures being considered an outlier. The reason for this was that during the COVID lockdowns in 2020, sales of fish for consumption decreased, and the surplus fish left in fish ponds were directed towards angler associations with state intervention and support, leading to more fish being stocked in natural waters than usual. In 2022, due to the spike in fish prices and other cost factors, stocking volumes were lower, but they still exceeded the quantities recorded in the catch statistics. When considering the average over several years, the balance shows a clear positive surplus. Over the four-year period, the stocked quantity exceeded the caught amount by 13-150%, with the average surplus for the entire period being 76%, and 86% in 2023, which can be considered a typical year from this perspective. The stocked quantity needs to compensate not only for the reported catch but also for illegal fishing and the natural mortality of the offspring. Meanwhile, the juveniles grow, which, when calculated by body weight, also contributes to maintaining the balance. There is significant variance in the actual stocked quantities, but its impact is either absent or only slightly present in the catch statistics.

The following figure shows the mandatory and actual stocking quantities by fish species. According to the Fisheries Management Plan, the required stocking quantity remains almost unchanged year by year, with the prescribed amount increasing only minimally. The majority of the prescribed quantity consists of one, two, or three-year-old carp (P1, P2, P3). KÖTIHESZ typically uses the funds allocated for exceeding the prescribed quantity to stock larger, three-year-old carp. The ratio of mandatory to actual stocking shows significant variations over the four years (-18 to +106%), with the total quantity stocked over the four-year period being 29% higher than the mandatory stocking quantity. The year 2023 is also representative in this regard, with an overachievement of +32%.

Figure 3 Obligatory and actual fish stocking on the Tisza

Source: KÖTIHESZ annual reports

It is worth examining how the species-specific stocking and catch statistics per unit area of the river developed between 2020 and 2023. The water area of the Tisza section belonging to KÖTIHESZ is a total of 2,511 hectares. The catch data were consistently 18-19 kg/ha every year, the mandatory stocking value ranged between 22-26 kg/ha, while the actual stocking value fluctuated between 21-45 kg/ha. Since the caught quantity and mandatory stocking values are relatively stable, their values compared to actual stocking follow the same trend over the years. In 2023, the actual stocked quantity exceeded the mandatory stocking value by 8 kg/ha, and the caught quantity by 16 kg/ha.

Figure 4 Stocking and catch per hectare on the Tisza

Source: KÖTIHESZ annual reports

In the cost-benefit analysis of fish spawning sites, it is important to examine how the species-specific values and the corresponding stocking costs relate to the fish replacement capacity per unit area of the spawning sites, as well as the maintenance and operational costs associated with them. In the subsequent analysis, we will compare these estimates to the 2023 values, as the catch and stocking data for the 2020-2023 period suggest that 2023 can be considered a representative year. Additionally, this is the most recent available data regarding the unit cost of fish procurement.

In 2023, KÖTIHESZ carried out fish replacement worth approximately 180 million HUF across the entire area (Donkó, 2025), a value that can be closely approximated by considering the purchased fish quantity at a unit price of 1,400 HUF/kg (totaling 168 million HUF), and the restocked juvenile perch at 45 HUF/individual (totaling 15 million HUF). The 1,400 HUF/kg unit price corresponds to a statement issued by MOHOSZ and MA-HAL in September 2023, which stated that "the price of 3-year-old, so-called market carp was set between 1,300-1,450 HUF/kg + VAT, depending on the quantity and transportation distance." Based on these calibrated unit values, the per-hectare stocking cost for the Tisza River can be determined: the estimated cost of mandatory stocking in 2023 was approximately 41,100 HUF/ha, while the actual stocking was carried out at a unit cost of 52,400 HUF/ha, meaning the additional stocking cost was about 11,300 HUF/ha. Using the same methodology, the value of the fish caught by anglers per unit area can also be calculated, which amounted to 25,100 HUF/ha.

4.1.3 Limitations of Replacing Excess Stocking

The successful operation of fish spawning sites can partly replace the stocking above the minimum quantity prescribed by the fisheries management plan. However, this is only possible if the flooding of the spawning sites occurs every year during the appropriate breeding period for each fish species. This is an uncertainty that the organisation responsible for fisheries management cannot integrate into its 5-year plan. The likelihood of flooding at individual

spawning sites can vary significantly; a good example of this is the Dobai and Fokorúpuszta areas: the Dobai spawning site represents a much larger area suitable for spawning for fish, but since it is located about 2 meters higher, its flooding can only happen at higher water levels, which occurs less frequently, while the smaller Fokorúpuszta spawning site is more likely to reach water levels suitable for spawning (Donkó, 2025).

Monoki and Nagy (2025) emphasized that when creating fish spawning sites, it is necessary to consider the current natural conditions and focus on areas where the Tisza River can more easily overflow, or where natural spawning sites are already functioning. These areas are currently threatened by several factors, so their protection is crucial for maintaining the reproductive capacity of the fish stock. The success of the spawning sites is not only influenced by the frequency of flooding, but also by factors such as their water retention capacity and size, as well as other important characteristics for fish reproduction. A successful spawning site can benefit from diverse water depths and banks, the presence of hiding places, and suitable vegetation. Some fish species prefer spawning on meadows, which was not a problem during spring floods in the past, especially in areas where regular grazing took place due to livestock farming. However, in the past few decades, both livestock populations and grazing areas have significantly decreased. Additionally, the fish's feeding conditions can be enhanced by certain tools, such as plankton ladders, thus increasing the success of spawning. However, this is not feasible for every spawning site.

Alongside natural effects and characteristics, it is necessary to mention the role of human intervention, which can have both negative and positive impacts on the operation of spawning sites. Proper operation of the spawning sites and water retention significantly affects the success of spawning. During the summer period, human intervention can play an important role as well: if the water level at the spawning site decreases, thus raising the water temperature, it is possible to increase oxygen levels by aerating and spraying the water, thus saving the fish (Guti, 2025). On the other hand, anglers targeting mature fish in the area can cause significant damage, but continuous monitoring of the water surface is costly and not practically feasible.

The surplus fish produced at spawning sites can only be estimated, which makes it difficult to integrate the associated benefits into the fisheries management plan. It is also important to consider that the positive effects of a successful spawning for anglers will only become apparent in the long term. Therefore, unlike stocking, anglers do not immediately see a return on their investment. For KÖTIHESZ, the satisfaction of its members (anglers) is an important aspect, so it strives to increase the fish stock in light of economic possibilities, with stocking being a suitable short-term tool. In the long term, however, fish spawning sites can reduce the necessary stocking amount, contributing to the natural reproductive capacity of the river's fish stock.

The values in the literature (Dorgai et al. 2005, Dorgai et al. 2006, Zsoldos 2024, Felvidéki 1982, Varga 2007, Todd et al. 2023, Wootton et al. 2023, Kenyeres 2016) vary significantly regarding the impact of 1 hectare of spawning site on the fish stock, especially in non-standing waters. The values in individual studies differ not only due to water type and area but also because of the range of fish species studied. The effect of a specific spawning site can only be determined through regular monitoring studies, but the results are difficult to generalise due to the numerous special habitat-specific characteristics mentioned earlier. According to the generally accepted estimate in Hungarian professional circles, 1 hectare of spawning site replaces 10 hectares of natural water surface biomass (Donkó, 2025). Regarding the spawning sites established in the floodplains of the Marcal and Rába rivers, experts estimated that a successful spawning could result in outcomes comparable to 5-10 stocking events (Ivancsóné Dr. Horváth, 2024). The total area of

water-covered spawning sites near Szolnok is approximately 200 hectares (Óballa, Doba, Bivalytó, Fokorúpuszta), so if we apply the previously mentioned estimate, these sites could replace the natural reproduction of 2,000 hectares of water surface, assuming successful flooding and spawning every year. The section of the Tisza River belonging to KÖTIHESZ covers a total area of 2,511 hectares.

The currently operating spawning sites are relatively small in comparison to the entire Central Tisza section, which represents a significant limitation. Although the individuals that hatch at the spawning sites and survive their first two summers create their living space along the longer stretches of the river, it is not realistic to expect one spawning site to have an effect over the entire length of the river. Therefore, in the case of KÖTIHESZ, it may still be justified to exceed the legally prescribed minimum stocking level on the stretches further from the spawning sites, even in cases of successful spawning.

4.1.4 The Ecological Role of Fish Spawning Sites

Both natural and human-made spawning sites are of critical importance for maintaining fish biodiversity, as greater species richness is observed during the reproductive processes compared to fish stocking. These areas can provide optimal breeding conditions for native species that are often pushed to the background in stocking programmes. Additionally, they increase genetic diversity within populations of species important for fish farming and recreational fishing, such as carp. According to the literature (Kenyeres, 2016) and monitoring results (Guti, 2025), it can be stated that fish that develop under natural conditions are more resilient, grow faster due to a more varied diet, and contribute to maintaining the stability of the local ecosystem, which, in the long term, supports sustainable fisheries management.

In spawning sites, not only native species reproduce, but also invasive fish species. The proportion of invasive juveniles depends on several factors. If the proportion of invasive species among the juveniles reaches a critical level (20%), the organisation responsible for fisheries management must select the juveniles before releasing them. A challenge here is that an initial monitoring study is required to estimate the proportion of invasive species. The presence of invasive juvenile fish at spawning sites presents a complex issue from several perspectives. From a conservation standpoint, these species can pose a threat to the local ecosystem, as they may compete with native species for food and habitat, thereby displacing native fish populations. On the other hand, invasive juvenile fish can play an important role in the food chain from another perspective. The young individuals can serve as food for predator fish, such as perch or catfish, and they also provide food for many waterfowl, including protected species. For predators like pike, which can tolerate oxygen-deprived water better, the spawning sites themselves can also serve as a food source. Due to this duality, our interviewees had differing opinions on the necessity of selecting invasive fish species.

Fish spawning sites are not only vital areas for fish reproduction but are also crucial for many other aquatic and riparian species. Amphibians often use these areas for feeding and reproduction, as shallow, vegetation-covered water creates ideal conditions for frogs, for example. Additionally, numerous examples demonstrate that the environment of spawning sites is of particular importance to waterfowl, as these areas often serve as breeding and feeding grounds. Quantifying the benefits of these additional ecosystem services is difficult, and for the purposes of this study, these advantages were not considered in the cost analysis.

4.2 Characteristics and Operational Experience of the Central Tisza Fish Spawning Sites

Before the 19th-century river regulation, there were numerous natural spawning sites along the Tisza, and without human intervention, the fish population was abundant. Fish reproduction and fishing/angling could be further enhanced with floodplain management. After the river regulation, the number of suitable spawning locations in the floodplain drastically decreased, and the changes in the water flow pattern did not help with fish population reproduction. In this context, the creation of new fish spawning sites through the relocation of embankments and the expansion of the floodplain has become of significant importance. Four such interventions have taken place in the Central Tisza: Óballa, Doba, and Fokorúpuszta above Szolnok, and Bivaly-tó below Szolnok. Additionally, two backwaters, Szóró and Kovácsi, can potentially be integrated into habitat rehabilitation, promoting fish reproduction. The map of the fish spawning sites and backwaters above Szolnok is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 5 Location of fish spawning sites and oxbow lakes above Szolnok

Source: Béla Horváth

This chapter presents the characteristics of the four floodplain areas suitable for fish spawning and the experience gained so far. At the end of the subsection, the flooding frequency of these areas is also discussed (section 4.2.5).

4.2.1 Óballa

Upstream of Szolnok, the furthest location from the city is the Óballa embankment relocation, which was created as part of the "Tisza Floodplain Project Phase I" (2017-2023). The total area brought into the floodplain is 160 hectares, of which 44 hectares are wetlands. The material used for embankment construction is suitable for fish spawning, and flooding begins at a water level of 350 cm (83.1 m above sea level) according to the Szolnok water gauge. The entire area is submerged at 560 cm (85.2 m above sea level). However, there is no restrictive closure structure, and thus the water cannot be regulated by a hydraulic structure; a wooden closure can be used to retain water. Due to its relatively low floodplain location, even smaller flood waves submerge the area. There is no monitoring data available regarding fish spawning.

4.2.2 Doba

Doba (Dobapuszta, Szórópuszta) is located almost opposite Óballa, on the right bank of the Tisza. The expansion of the floodplain, similar to the Óballa area, was created as part of the "Tisza Floodplain Project Phase I" (2017-2023). The Hungarian National Angling Federation (MOHOSZ) successfully applied for support from the Hungarian Fisheries Operational Programme for the establishment of technical facilities needed for the operation of the wetland. The total cost was 119 million HUF, with a 50% non-refundable grant. When the application was submitted, KÖTIVIZIG and MOHOSZ agreed on the use of the area, which came into effect after the application was successful. According to the agreement, the area and, after construction, the hydraulic structure with a water law permit were operated by the KÖTIHESZ. The agreement remains valid until the end of the maintenance period of the structure. In practice, the operation is primarily guided by fisheries management objectives. According to the agreement, the use of the property is free of charge, and the user must take the interests of the Asset Management (KÖTIVIZIG) into account during construction and operation, notify them about repair and maintenance work, and the agreement specifies that the parties will not cause damage to each other, or if they do, they will be liable for compensation. The agreement does not mention the operating procedures of the structure, but the detailed operational rules are part of the water law permit documentation.

As a result of the floodplain expansion project, the total area brought into the floodplain is 200 hectares, of which 57 hectares are wetlands. This is the highest-lying fish spawning site, and flooding occurs at a water level between 620-740 cm on the Szolnok water gauge (85.3-86.5 m above sea level). However, such high water levels occur relatively infrequently, as indicated by the tables in section 3.3.5. The threshold level of the hydraulic structure is also 85.3 m above sea level.

Under the agreement between KÖTIHESZ and KÖTIVIZIG, the operator of the area, the fish spawning site has been operated since 2020, with significant experience gathered over the past five years. The annual operating cost is approximately 5 million HUF, and a separate line item in the KÖTIHESZ budget is allocated for the Doba fish spawning site. The annual costs primarily cover maintenance expenses, including mowing the riverbank, dredging the silt after silting, expert fees for fish monitoring and plankton studies, the opening and closing of the hydraulic structure, maintenance, and sorting the juveniles with a focus on invasive species. The installation of culverts was also an additional cost.

Since the establishment of the fish spawning site, two flood waves have occurred that flooded the area: in early 2023 and then from January to March 2024, as shown in the table below. During the 2023 winter flood, weather conditions were suboptimal for spawning, while the spring 2024 weather was more favourable. Despite monitoring efforts, no quantitative results are available on the effects of the flooding. Due to their small size, the fish could not be tagged for tracking, and there was no way to measure the fish quantity. However, the juvenile fish were visible to the naked eye, particularly in 2024, and the activity of wading birds also indicated that the flooding had a positive effect on the fish population.

The angling federation is aware that successful spawning has many prerequisites, and it is unlikely that all conditions will perfectly align during a given flood. The expectation is that several moderately successful floods may precede the optimal case, where many years of work may pay off at once, and multiple years' worth of juveniles enter the river. Unlike other fish spawning sites, the expectation here is that although flooding occurs less frequently, it is richer in juveniles (a dense penny vs. a rare forint). Bison are grazed on the area, which also supports successful spawning if all other conditions are favourable.

Table 2 Doba fish spawning site flooding statistics 2023-2024

Starting date	End date	Starting water level	Ending water level	Flooded area (ha)
Filling the fish spawning area				
30 Jan 2023	2 Feb 2023	0	77	35
10 Jan 2024	16 Jan 2024	70	88	60
16 Feb 2024	10 Mar 2024	80	102	71
Releasing water back to the river				
18 Jun 2024	21 Jun 2024	60	30	23
4 Jul 2024	5 Jul 2024	30	0	12

Source: Béla Horváth (2025)

The fish spawning site has several conservation-related connections. On the one hand, if the proportion of invasive species among the juveniles exceeds 20%, they must be sorted before being released, using a sorting table and manual labor. Since there was no significant juvenile population in 2023 and 2024, such a survey – and potential sorting – did not take place. However, conservation benefits were observed. On the one hand, waterfowl enthusiastically visited the spawning site, where they found food, and on the other hand, after the late winter flooding of 2023, significant amphibian reproduction was observed. As a result, the environmental protection authority (HNPI) requested that the water and juvenile release be postponed. The wetland is also frequently visited by wildlife, mainly wild boar, wild ducks, geese, and foxes.

From the perspective of fishermen, however, the conservation benefits also present a conflict, as birds can decimate the juvenile population, and amphibians may delay the release of juveniles into the river.

Regarding the fish population's diversity and the altered resistance compared to the stocked juveniles, there are currently only assumptions, with no monitoring data available.

Finally, there was also an attempt to introduce mature breeding pairs to the fish spawning site. These are fish that have been caught by fishermen, overwintered, and hormonally "stimulated." Although this method may potentially lead to significant juvenile production, the drawback is that if fishermen catch the large, mature individuals, they typically do not release them, thus preventing reproduction. The federation lacks the resources to prevent the catch and removal of breeding fish.

The assessment of Doba's operation among the anglers is not unanimous. Those who are familiar with the fish spawning site do not necessarily see short-term positive effects, and the long-term benefits are of lesser interest to most fishermen.

4.2.3 Bivaly Lake

Bivaly Lake is a relatively low-lying area, with a terrain elevation of 350-550 cm (82-84 m above sea level) on the Szolnok water gauge, meaning it is flooded more frequently than other fish spawning sites. The total area of the floodplain is 450 ha, of which 89 ha is a wetland habitat. The floodplain expansion was created under the "Bivaly Lake Embankment Relocation" project, however, the infrastructure for the full operation of the habitat is missing. The old estuary sluice located at 83.10 m above sea level allows partial regulation of the water level. Despite this, the conditions are still favourable for fish spawning.

The embankment relocation occurred in 2008, and since then, there have been several flooding events that submerged the area, enabling fish spawning and monitoring of the process. During these floods, particularly large amounts of juveniles were produced, and experience has shown that the area is excellent for fish spawning both from a fish physiology and water quality perspective. After favourable flood events between 2016-2018, a significant proportion of carp was observed, which is favourable from a fishing perspective. However, invasive species, such as the silver crucian carp (*Carassius gibelio*), also appeared in large numbers among the juveniles. Conflicting information was received from various sources regarding whether native or invasive species dominated the area. According to experts from the HNPI, in certain years, such as 2017 and 2019, bighead carp (*Hypophthalmichthys nobilis*) also successfully spawned in the area, contributing to the currently excessive bighead carp population in the Tisza. (Bighead carp typically spawn in the main channel of the river, but specimens that drift out to the floodplain can sometimes appear in massive numbers. This serves as a trap for the fish, while it presents an opportunity for the fisheries management.)

Plans for organising and operating the area as a fish spawning site are already available. These plans include the restoration of the old flood protection sluice, the reconstruction of the Fényes-tó channel lock, and the modernization of the water retention and drainage systems. Besides technical solutions, grazing is also important. The area has been leased for grazing grey cattle and buffalo. The livestock maintains the vegetation, reducing the roughness of the area, which is crucial for floodwater drainage. Their manure can also form the base of the food chain for the juveniles.

4.2.4 Fokorúpuszta

The floodplain expansion was created under the "Tisza Floodplain Project Phase II" and included the construction of the technical facilities necessary for operating the wetland. The total area of

the floodplain is 285 ha, of which 23 ha is a wetland habitat. With a terrain elevation of 380-500 cm (82.8-84 m above sea level) on the Szolnok water gauge, flooding is expected relatively frequently but less often than at Bivaly Lake. The threshold level of the inlet-outlet structure is 82.80 m above sea level. The technical facilities related to the wetland are currently operated by the water authority, but it would be more beneficial for the fishermen's association to manage the fish spawning site. At one end of the spawning site, the HNPI has created a nesting site for marsh harriers, which the birds have started using.

KÖTIHESZ does not shy away from managing the fish spawning site. They contacted the water authority two years ago about this, but the negotiations did not progress. After a flood wave, water retention is likely to occur informally for now. KÖTIHESZ has previously been active in the area, with tasks such as mowing, which the water authority appreciates. The mowing covered the area typically used by fishermen, while the section where birds nest was not mowed at the request of conservationists, which also helps keep fishermen away. The stakeholders agree that it would be beneficial to formalize the parameters of cooperation and record them in an agreement. For this, an agreement between KÖTIVIZIG and KÖTIHESZ would be necessary, but the HNPI's involvement also arises.

The following maps illustrate the flooding of the area in 2024.

Figure 6 The Fokorúpuszta fish spawning site before, during, and after the 2024 flood wave

The next map illustrates the direction in which water from the fish spawning site can flow towards the Kovácsi oxbow lake.

Figure 7 The relationship between the Fokorúpuszta fish spawning site and the Kovácsí oxbow lake

4.2.5 Frequency of Flooding at Each Site

In the previous subsections, we discussed the minimum water level (measured at the Szolnok gauge) at which flooding begins at each fish spawning site. In this subsection, based on 25 years of water level time series data, we present for all four fish spawning sites how many days in each year the Tisza's water level reached or exceeded this threshold value.

Table 3 illustrates that the highest-elevation site, the Doba spawning ground, is submerged less frequently and for shorter durations compared to the other three locations. From this perspective, the positioning of Óballa and Bivaly Lake is the most favourable. The table also highlights that - consistent with broader experiences of Tisza river floods - the decade starting from the year 2000 was characterised by higher water levels than the subsequent period.

Table 3 Number of days with water level above the flooding threshold at each spawning site, 2000–2024

	Number of days with water level above the flooding threshold			
	Óballa	Doba	Fokorú	Bivaly-tó
Threshold water level at the Szolnok water gauge (cm)	350	620	380	350
2000	89	63	83	89
2001	104	33	88	104
2002	75	26	68	75
2003	22	0	19	22
2004	76	31	71	76
2005	97	70	89	97
2006	133	75	128	133
2007	67	16	60	67
2008	82	15	77	82
2009	56	0	44	56
2010	194	103	184	194
2011	54	30	48	54
2012	20	0	13	20
2013	75	49	71	75
2014	0	0	0	0
2015	15	0	13	15
2016	56	23	50	56
2017	52	5	50	52
2018	68	18	66	68
2019	36	9	31	36
2020	38	0	33	38
2021	91	23	77	91
2022	58	0	52	58
2023	110	33	101	110
2024	80	45	72	80

Table 4 illustrates the seasonality of flooding. The greatest likelihood for prolonged inundation occurs during the first four months of the year, which is also favourable from a fish physiological perspective. Different fish species spawn at different times of the year - for instance, pike lay eggs as early as February–March, even in cold water, while zander typically spawn in April. Other species, such as carp or catfish, spawn in late spring or early summer. Water retained at spawning sites after a late-winter or early-spring flood can be ideal for reproduction.

Table 4 Average monthly number of days with water level above the flooding threshold at each spawning site (2000–2024)

	Number of days with water level above the flooding threshold			
	Óballa	Doba	Fokorú	Bivaly-tó
Threshold water level at the Szolnok water gauge (cm)	350	620	380	350
Month				
1	8.4	3.3	7.8	8.4
2	10.0	3.0	9.1	10.0
3	16.6	5.2	15.4	16.6
4	12.7	7.3	11.6	12.7
5	6.6	3.0	5.9	6.6
6	4.6	2.6	4.2	4.6
7	1.8	0.3	1.7	1.8
8	1.5	0.2	1.4	1.5
9	0.5	0.0	0.1	0.5
10	0.2	0.0	0.2	0.2
11	2.3	0.0	1.7	2.3
12	4.6	1.9	4.4	4.6

The following tables break down the data by spawning site, showing how many days per month in each year the water level exceeded the flooding threshold. If the level rises only slightly above the threshold for just a few days, flooding may not be sufficient, and the number of reproductively viable individuals reaching the site may remain low. In contrast, longer periods of inundation - lasting at least 5–10 days in late winter or spring - significantly improve the chances of successful reproduction.

Table 7 Monthly number of days above the flooding threshold for Fokorúpuszta (2000–2024)

Fokorú	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
380	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
2000	0	18	21	30	24	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2001	5	7	25	21	4	6	6	5	0	0	9	0
2002	1	28	26	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	9	0
2003	6	0	10	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2004	0	3	17	30	3	0	0	3	0	0	7	8
2005	0	1	15	30	31	5	0	4	3	0	0	0
2006	9	3	28	30	22	30	6	0	0	0	0	0
2007	11	25	22	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2008	0	0	27	20	8	0	5	10	0	0	0	7
2009	5	4	15	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	4
2010	27	6	22	18	17	30	18	12	0	0	4	30
2011	31	4	11	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2012	0	0	7	3	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
2013	0	3	19	30	11	8	0	0	0	0	0	0
2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2015	5	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0
2016	6	21	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0
2017	0	17	17	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16
2018	15	8	18	25	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2019	0	0	4	0	11	11	0	0	0	0	0	0
2020	0	4	11	0	0	10	7	0	0	0	0	0
2021	11	28	14	1	21	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
2022	11	6	0	15	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	17
2023	18	15	21	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	28
2024	31	27	10	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

4.3 Grazing in the Floodplain

In addition to fish spawning habitats, grazing is another logical use of newly created areas resulting from floodplain expansion. It is worth briefly addressing this, as grazing in the immediate surroundings of spawning habitats may also have significance from a fish-physiological perspective.

Grazing is not only a form of land use but also provides indirect ecological and flood protection benefits. However, its actual implementation depends significantly on local conditions, business considerations, and partly on the institutional and legal framework.

Over the past decades, livestock farming has declined in the region, especially traditional, pasture-based forms. Few local residents keep animals, and most livestock farmers work in intensive, stable-based systems, using enclosures rather than open grazing. Willingness to graze is relatively low; animals are often brought in from farther away, sometimes by truck rather than being herded.

Following the relocation of flood embankments, the newly managed areas under the water authority could not be leased under revenue-generating agreements during the first five years due to constraints from supported projects. However, this restriction has since been lifted. The areas offered for lease are generally successfully utilized—leased for both mowing and grazing. Longer-term, five-year contracts are more in demand than annual agreements, as they provide greater

predictability for farmers. Rental fees are typically low, mainly due to low demand for pastureland. Often, so-called "positive-zero" contracts are concluded (e.g., 1,000 HUF/ha/year). At this price, it is worthwhile for farmers to use the land, but they would not pay much more, as the floodplain status involves risks: animals must be removed before floods, and prolonged inundation can temporarily prevent grazing. However, the presence of water can be an advantage, as watering animals is often easier here than on the protected side of the levee. For the water authority, leasing the land reduces mowing costs—important from a flood protection perspective—making these agreements mutually beneficial overall.

Floodplain grazing is not entirely free of conflict, but the number of problematic situations can be reduced with experience. Due to the lack of electric fences, animals sometimes wander off, occasionally entering agricultural fields and damaging crops. There have also been instances where animals frightened people in the floodplain, such as local anglers—this is especially true for large-bodied buffalo.

The impact of grazing goes beyond agricultural and flood protection benefits—it can also offer significant ecological advantages. Several fish species prefer to spawn in shallow, flooded grassy areas. The organic manure produced by grazing provides nutrients for aquatic plankton, which serve as a primary food source for fish fry. This effect is similar to the fertilization of fishponds, where plankton production is intentionally enhanced.

5 Economic Aspects of Operating the Fish Spawning Habitat at Fokorúpuszta

In this chapter, we explore whether, based on the available experience, estimated costs, and expected benefits, it is economically worthwhile for the anglers' association to actively operate the fish spawning site at Fokorúpuszta from a fishery management perspective. Importantly, the investment costs - covered by the "Tisza Floodplain Project Phase II" - were not borne by the anglers' association. For the full picture we also examine the economic viability of the fish spawning habitat under the assumption that the association would be responsible for covering all costs, including the initial investment. At the same time, one should note that there is also a variety of „in-between” solutions of public source financing (for example from EU ecological restoration funds) that can provide the cost of the necessary infrastructure development.

5.1 Unit Costs of Spawning Habitats Compared to Stocking Costs

In comparison to the previously presented unit costs of fish stocking, it is worth examining the unit costs associated with operating the Fokorúpuszta spawning site. This can be done by calculating the estimated annual operational costs of the spawning habitat and projecting them onto the area of the river where the habitat is expected to maintain the fish stock's reproductive capacity. Specifically, this refers to the water surface area that the spawning site can effectively serve.

For this calculation, we apply the guideline from the study in the "Fisheries Utilization Program Package," which states: 1 hectare of spawning habitat replaces fish stocking on 10 hectares of natural water surface.

To enable this comparison, it is necessary to estimate the annual operational costs of the spawning habitat. In determining the costs, we considered maintenance, periodic reconstruction (required approximately every 10 years), operation of the infrastructure, fish stocking and possible sorting (e.g., removing invasive species), as well as professional management. For each cost item, we defined both a minimum and maximum annual cost level.

Costs that occur periodically were annualized based on their frequency, so all cost items are expressed as average annual values, even though actual yearly expenditures may vary. The detailed estimates are presented in the following table:

Table 8 Cost structure of operating the Fokorúpuszta spawning habitat

	Minimum annual cost (HUF)	Maximum annual cost (HUF)
Maintenance: labor	30 000	60 000
Maintenance: material costs	200 000	400 000
Reconstruction	40 000	100 000
Operation of facilities (sluice opening/closing, assuming average year)	60 000	120 000
Operation of facilities (fish monitoring, assuming average year)	160 000	240 000
Fish sorting, if needed before releasing to the river	60 000	60 000
Introduction of mature breeding pairs	100 000	200 000
Professional management: labor	800 000	1 100 000
Professional management: material costs	500 000	687 500
Total	1 950 000	2 967 500
Unit cost per hectare (HUF/ha)	84 783	129 022

Source: Béla Horváth (2025), and own calculations.

Based on our estimates, the annual operational cost of the Fokorúpuszta spawning site ranges between 1.9 and 3.0 million HUF. The estimated annual cost per hectare of spawning habitat is approximately 85,000 - 130,000 HUF, which can be compared to the actual unit cost of the Doba spawning site (5 million HUF total), which comes to 88,000 HUF/ha - falling within the same range.

A key parameter in comparing spawning site costs is the assumed frequency of successful spawning. If spawning is successful every year, the previously calculated unit annual cost (85,000–130,000 HUF/ha) can be projected onto 10 hectares of river surface per hectare of spawning area—reflecting its potential to fully replace stocking each year. This results in a unit cost per hectare of river between 8,500 and 13,000 HUF annually.

Conversely, if spawning is only successful once every 10 years, then the 10 years' worth of costs must be allocated to just one successful replenishment, meaning the unit cost per hectare of river would be 85,000 - 130,000 HUF.

Due to uncertainty regarding the frequency of successful spawning, we assessed several scenarios—assuming success every year, every 3 years, every 5 years, and every 10 years. The graph below illustrates the unit operational costs per hectare of river under each scenario, and how they compare to the cost of traditional fish stocking:

Figure 8 Annual unit costs of spawning sites, projected to the Tisza river area replenished with juvenile fish

The results show that if spawning is successful once every 3 years, then under all cost assumptions (minimum, Doba-based, and maximum: 25,435–38,707 HUF/ha), spawning habitats are more cost-effective than stocking.

With spawning every 5 years, the lower-bound estimate for Fokorúpuszta (42,391 HUF/ha) and the Doba actual cost (43,860 HUF/ha) are roughly equivalent to the mandatory stocking cost (41,071 HUF/ha). However, using the higher-end cost estimate (64,511 HUF/ha), spawning becomes more expensive than actual stocking costs (52,393 HUF/ha).

In summary, if spawning occurs successfully every 3 to 5 years, the unit cost of maintaining fish populations using spawning habitats is comparable to or more favourable than stocking. Since mandatory stocking must be carried out by the anglers' association regardless, spawning sites offer a significant opportunity to optimize or reduce additional stocking costs.

From a financial perspective, our analysis indicates that it is worthwhile to allocate part of the additional stocking budget toward maintaining spawning sites, as this may result in greater fish reproduction over time - even if not every year, then on average, assuming spawning succeeds at least every 5 years.

As previously noted, the investment costs were covered by the "Tisza Floodplain Project Phase II" and were not borne by the anglers' association. The construction of the spawning habitat was an integral part of the dike relocation project and came at a cost of HUF 1.1 billion. If this expense were included in the cost-benefit analysis, total costs would substantially exceed the benefits - even at a 0% discount rate, as shown in Table 9 . Applying a higher discount rate or assuming that successful spawning occurs less frequently than annually would further diminish the investment's economic viability.

Table 9 Net present value of the Fokorúpuszta fish spawning site under different scenarios

	No investment cost included, minimum operating cost	Investment cost included, minimum operating cost	No investment cost included, maximum operating cost	Investment cost included, maximum operating cost
Investment cost (HUF)	0	-1,100,000,000	0	-1,100,000,000
Annualised operating cost (HUF)	-1,950,000	-1,950,000	-2,967,500	-2,967,500
Annualised benefit (HUF) - assuming successful spawning each year	12,050,479	12,050,479	12,050,479	12,050,479
Discount rate	0%	0%	0%	0%
Net present value for 15 years (HUF)	151,507,192	-948,492,808	136,244,692	-963,755,308

	No investment cost included, minimum operating cost	Investment cost included, minimum operating cost	No investment cost included, maximum operating cost	Investment cost included, maximum operating cost
Investment cost (HUF)	0	-1,100,000,000	0	-1,100,000,000
Annualised operating cost (HUF)	-1,950,000	-1,950,000	-2,967,500	-2,967,500
Annualised benefit (HUF) - assuming successful spawning every 5 years	2,410,096	2,410,096	2,410,096	2,410,096
Discount rate	3%	3%	3%	3%
Net present value for 15 years (HUF)	5,492,595	-1,094,507,405	-6,654,254	-1,106,654,254

5.2 Cost-Benefit Assessment of Spawning Sites within a Fish Biology Framework

In the case of Fokorúpuszta, we also examined the potential economic surplus generated by the spawning site when its output is estimated through a fish biology approach. For the estimate, we used the data from the articles mentioned in section 4.1.3, estimates by Béla Horváth (2025), and current market prices from aquaculture enterprises. The parameters and calculation steps used in the estimation are summarized in the following table:

Table 10 Economic value of juvenile fish produced by the Fokorúpuszta spawning site

Parameter	Unit	Value	Note
Average carp weight	kg	3	
Specific egg number per brood carp	eggs/kg	133,333	
Egg number per brood carp	eggs/fish	400,000	Typically ranges between 200,000–1,500,000 eggs
Fertilized eggs	eggs/fish	360,000	Fertilization rate 80–95%; applied value: 90%
Hatched larvae	larvae/fish	330,000	Hatching rate from fertilized eggs: 90–95%; applied rate: 92%
First breathing stage	fish/fish	300,000	Survival rate: 90–95%; applied value: 91%
Yearlings surviving first year	fish/fish	3,000	Survival rate under pond conditions: 5–30%; we applied a very conservative 1%
Number of broodstock using the site	fish	100	Broodstock expected to use the Fokorúpuszta site
Yearling carp produced at the site	fish	300,000	
Weight of yearling carp	kg/fish	0.03	Based on literature and pond data: 20–100g; applied: 30g as conservative estimate. For cyprinids: 15g
Total carp biomass produced	kg	9,000	
Unit cost of yearling carp	HUF/kg	950	Based on available aquaculture market prices; for cyprinids: 500 HUF/kg
Value produced in case of successful spawning	HUF/year	8,550,000	For cyprinids (e.g., roach, bream): 2,250,000 HUF

Source: Béla Horváth (2025) and own calculations.

In this estimation, we primarily considered the value generated through carp reproduction, but we also calculated a version that includes the value of successful spawning of cyprinid species. According to the estimate, in the case of successful spawning, the value of yearling carp produced at the Fokorúpuszta spawning site would be 8,550,000 HUF, and including cyprinids, the total economic value would be 10,800,000 HUF.

These values were then compared to the minimum and maximum estimated annual operational costs of the spawning site. The following table shows the net difference between the produced value and maintenance costs under different frequencies of successful spawning:

Table 11 Difference between economic value of fish stock and maintenance costs (HUF/year)

Successful spawning	Max cost – carp only	Max cost – carp + cyprinids	Min cost – carp only	Min cost – carp + cyprinids
Every 10 years	-2,112,500	-1,887,500	-1,095,000	-870,000
Every 5 years	-1,257,500	-807,500	-240,000	210,000
Every 3 years	-117,500	632,500	900,000	1,650,000
Every year	5,582,500	7,832,500	6,600,000	8,850,000

Source: Own calculations

The results indicate that if spawning occurs successfully every 3–5 years, the economic value of the spawning site becomes positive, meaning it generates more value than its maintenance costs.

It is worth noting that in several parts of the value estimation we used conservative/pessimistic assumptions (see Table 9). With more favourable survival rates, a higher number of fry per hectare, or larger average yearling weights, the resulting economic value could be significantly higher.

6 Preparing an Agreement on the Operation of the Fokorúpuszta Spawning Site

This chapter reviews the issues that stakeholders should jointly consider when establishing a long-term agreement for the operation of a spawning site. First, based primarily on interviews conducted during the project, we summarize how the organizations with an interest in spawning sites perceive them, what they expect, and what conflicts of interest may arise. Then we discuss the principles that can help resolve these conflicts and support the formation of a shared position. Since the operational agreement is a legal document, we highlight key legal issues that need to be addressed. Finally, we illustrate what the practical operation of the Fokorúpuszta spawning site might look like. While it is not necessary to include the detailed operational plan in the agreement, it can support prior joint planning.

6.1 Stakeholder Interests Related to Spawning Sites

We identified three stakeholder groups with different interests related to the spawning sites: the angling association, nature conservation, and the water management authority. We conducted interviews with representatives of each to better understand their positions, expectations, and potential conflicts. Overall, we found that the existence and operation of spawning sites align with the goals of all three groups, though certain conflicts or opposing interests may still arise that must be addressed to maximize public benefit and reduce dissatisfaction.

KÖTIVIZIG's regional interests primarily relate to flood risk reduction and improving conditions for flood protection. Additional water security, regional water supply, and water quality goals are also relevant and are influenced by land use in the floodplain (e.g., pollution from cultivation). The creation and proper operation of spawning sites generally support water management tasks rather than hinder them:

- In flood events, ensuring rapid and safe drainage is key. Spawning sites do not obstruct this, and in fact, the floodplain expansion (e.g., levee relocation) that enables them reduces flood risk—as demonstrated in the Danube Floodplain Project (see Chapter 2).
- Maintaining low roughness in the floodplain is important, but spawning sites have little effect on this. Grazing and mowing have greater roles, and organizing/mobilizing these is the water authority's responsibility. These functions are compatible—and even desirable—for the operation of spawning sites.
- Spawning sites also contribute to water retention, which aligns with water management goals by supporting infiltration and evaporation—both improving the regional water balance.
- According to water management experts, spawning sites should be operated by the angling association, as is currently the case at Doba.

The Angling Association and, indirectly, the angling community can benefit in various ways from the proper operation of spawning sites, though conflicts may also arise:

- Spawning sites offer a natural, low-cost means of restocking fish populations and can partly replace the stocking of fry from fish farms, saving costs. However, the association views its mission as stocking as much fish as its budget allows, and sees natural spawning as an additional, rather than alternative, source. This is reinforced by the

awareness at KÖTIHESZ of the stochastic nature of spawning—after several weak years, one strong year could bring an abundance of fry.

- Operational and maintenance costs of the spawning sites are significant but not disproportionate. The association considers it worthwhile to invest in this activity.
- Maintaining the genetic diversity of native species may be an added benefit, although there is still limited evidence from the Middle Tisza on which species successfully spawn.
- While the association has a positive attitude toward operating the sites, most anglers are unaware of them. Since benefits only appear after several years even in the case of successful spawning, they are largely indifferent to the existence or success of the sites.
- A conflict may arise if members fish in the spawning site. Despite being prohibited, this can happen, and the association lacks resources to provide constant (or even regular) supervision at the site.

HNPI, the regional nature conservation authority:

- Overall, it views the spawning sites positively. Despite potential conservation risks, they are preferred over stocking, which can degrade the genetic composition of the fish population and reduce native species' share.
- HNPI is concerned that invasive species may reproduce more successfully than natives. If their proportion exceeds 20%, the fry cannot be released into the river. This could be addressed through sorting or targeted harvesting. However, sorting may also harm native fry, which are vulnerable to air exposure during the process. Still, if invasive levels are low, conservation authorities would favour spawning sites over stocking.
- Successful spawning at the sites clearly supports the feeding and reproduction of wading birds—this is a conservation benefit but a disadvantage from the angling perspective due to fish loss.
- The reproduction of amphibians and other protected species at the sites is also a conservation gain but could become a source of conflict if conservation wishes to delay the drainage of water, whereas fish biology would require earlier release.
- Protected bird nesting sites may be disturbed by anglers; therefore, conservation would prefer to ban angling on or in parts of the spawning sites.

Grazing is supported and welcomed by all stakeholders.

In summary, water management, nature conservation, and angling all support the establishment and operation of spawning sites. However, some conflicts of interest arise—primarily between anglers and conservation—which should be addressed:

- The question of the proportion and role of invasive species could be clarified through monitoring, helping determine accurate ratios and understand the ecological impacts of larger invasive fry populations (e.g., whether they shift the river's ecological balance or serve as food for predatory fish or birds).
- Conflict may arise regarding the timing of releasing fish into the river, as conservation and fisheries may have different optimal periods for this.
- Wading birds' fish consumption reduces the number of fish available for anglers.
- Finally, the presence of anglers at the spawning sites is problematic for both the angling association and conservationists.

6.2 Principles for Developing the Agreement

The floodplain holds significant importance and potential in sustaining the fish populations of natural aquatic ecosystems. This potential is especially great when natural conditions are supported by an active managing organization that helps overcome local or situational reproductive limitations. Our analysis shows that within the framework of the Fisheries Act, there is legal support for operating and managing natural fish spawning sites. Successful operation, however, requires not only economic feasibility but also the resolution of other organizational and institutional conditions. This chapter focuses on presenting the key elements necessary for such successful agreements.

In our case, the operation of natural spawning sites requires smooth cooperation among three organizations: the fisheries manager of the area, the competent water management authority, and the national park. The water authority plays a dual role: it is both a professional stakeholder and the property manager of the land in question. The national park is responsible for enforcing conservation considerations.

In the KÖTIVIZIG region, it is already a tradition that management codes (or “Codes”) are drawn up for important water bodies involving many stakeholders. These codes help maintain operational balance among various use expectations and serve as guiding documents to which the regionally involved organizations can commit. A similar framework agreement is recommended for the three organizations in this case, outlining jointly accepted principles for spawning site operation, monitoring procedures, and professional coordination. This framework agreement, along with subsequent annual activity plans, can provide the technical support needed for the fisheries manager to carry out activities authorized under sections 49.§ e), f), and g) of the fisheries management plan.

Below we provide recommendations on what types of activities and authorizations the parties should consider agreeing on.

Proper functioning of spawning sites is in the interest of all parties. While the primary focus of the agreement is fish reproduction, the operation of the site also serves the unique mandates of the state partners and can support multiple activities and processes that provide broader community value. Therefore, similar to the temporary agreement between Kötivizig and Kötihesz regarding the operation of the Doba spawning site, it is recommended to state explicitly that the physical infrastructure needed to operate the spawning site can be used free of charge by the managing organization.

The fisheries manager has a legal obligation to offset the impacts of fishing activities on fish populations and to preserve natural aquatic ecosystems. This dual obligation can best be fulfilled by combining fish pond restocking with efforts to support natural reproduction. The expectations of the angling community and conservation groups regarding fish population composition differ, so these two restocking methods should not be seen as mutually exclusive but as complementary in varying proportions. This approach is supported by available data and expert estimates, which suggest that over the long term, operating natural spawning sites is a financially viable activity if their operating costs are compared to the costs of fish pond restocking they replace.

Another key consideration is that the “transaction costs” of operation should remain low—that is, fieldwork should be easy to plan, require minimal administration and bureaucracy, and not be hindered by the lack of consensus or decision-making by multiple stakeholders, or by missing

information. Therefore, the following elements related to key operational phases should be included in the agreement:

During the filling period, the water management authority, based on its flood forecasting operations, often has information several days—or even a week—in advance regarding the timing and duration of water levels expected to exceed the threshold levels of hydraulic structures. Through the agreement, this information can be shared with the fisheries manager, who can then better schedule access to sites and the handling of the infrastructure.

During the water retention and drainage period, uncertainties arising from prioritizing conservation considerations can cause delayed interventions and the loss of fish fry. The goal is to balance three objectives: maximizing natural fish reproduction, preventing the spread of invasive species, and supporting local ecosystem conservation goals (e.g. improving feeding opportunities for protected birds that feed on fry, or supporting amphibian reproduction). Aligning these goals may require a shared, long-term monitoring program that produces data for situational assessments. The purpose of this is not necessarily to make or approve specific operational decisions, but rather to develop guiding principles and shared preferences to inform decision-making.

Based on the discussions, we encountered a wide range of opinions and expectations regarding the species composition and reproductive success of the spawning sites. However, these views were generally based on one or two specific, more thoroughly documented events. We believe that such information is insufficient for comprehensive operational decision-making—especially considering that ad hoc decisions may come with significant time (missed opportunities) and financial costs.

Synthesizing these opinions, we propose a shared perspective based on the assumption that natural spawning sites will reflect the species composition characteristic of the river. Trying to alter this through selection at the spawning site may cause more harm to the overall fish population than if resources were instead invested in activities that improve the status of native species—ultimately influencing their reproductive success in the floodplain spawning site as well.

One possible element of the agreement could be that if the spawning site has had little reproductive success in recent years (e.g., only one successful year out of the past five), and this jeopardizes the financial viability of its operation, then the offspring of that year should be released into the river—regardless of the exact species composition.

During the resting/maintenance period, it is advisable to document the experiences of the given year and agree on them collectively. These experiences can then inform fine-tuning of the operational rules.

We also recommend allocating resources—via formal commitments—for monitoring the spawning site and riverine fish populations and for harmonizing the sampling methodologies currently used by various organizations. Structured data collection would greatly improve understanding of the spawning site's effectiveness and its impact on the river section's fish population, which in turn would support more satisfactory operational decisions for all stakeholders.

Understanding the spawning site's impact on the riverine fish population may also expand the fisheries manager's range of decision-making options in future years—such as in 2022—when the financial burden of mandatory restocking could spike significantly.

An annual joint evaluation of the processes would allow stakeholders to review longer-term trends in connection with the five-year renewal cycle of the fisheries management plan, and to formulate strategic recommendations. These could be incorporated into the plan, supporting smoother spawning site operations in the upcoming period.

Although the timing of review cycles does not fully align, the seven-year review cycle of the National River Basin Management Plan yields a wealth of new information on the ecological status of river sections, hydromorphological changes, and variations in flood frequency—all of which are key boundary conditions for the successful operation of spawning sites. It is therefore essential to incorporate any changes in these conditions into the fisheries plan renewal process, so that operational expectations remain realistic.

Although it may not require a formal multilateral agreement, we believe the issue of angling at the spawning site should also be addressed in this framework. According to interviews, angling is allowed at spawning sites just like on other water bodies, although this endangers spawning success—or at least its extent—in at least two ways: one is the capture of fish introduced to assist egg-laying, the other is the risk of algal blooms caused by baiting during periods prone to oxygen deficiency. It may be worthwhile to develop a program based on "extra responsibilities in exchange for extra opportunities" for a group of committed anglers. These anglers would gain the right to fish at the spawning site by participating in a training session explaining how the site operates, and by committing to avoid baiting, release ripe fish, and promote compliance with these rules. The "socialization" of regular on-site supervision could benefit all parties involved.

6.3 Contractual Frameworks

There is already an agreement in place regarding the operation of the Dobai spawning site—although it will expire at the end of the investment maintenance period (within a year), and its renewal will soon be due. This agreement can serve as a model for the Fokorúpuszta agreement as well.

The Dobai agreement stipulates that KÖTIVIZIG, as the asset manager, provides the land owned by the Hungarian State to the Hungarian National Anglers' Association (MOHOSZ), acting as the investor and operator, for the purpose of establishing a spawning site and a nursery for juvenile fish. The agreement was necessitated by the grant application used to finance the investment.

Among other things, the agreement includes the following provisions:

- MOHOSZ may use the land free of charge,
- it must consider the owner's interests during maintenance activities,
- at the end of the agreement term, the site must be left in an orderly condition,
- MOHOSZ assumes responsibility for any damage it causes,
- it must notify the asset manager in advance of any work to be carried out on the site,
- it bears all costs related to the facilities,
- and it is not entitled to any registration in the land registry.

The asset manager commits to ensuring that its own activities do not harm the MOHOSZ facilities, to respect their safety, and to tolerate third-party entry onto the site for construction and maintenance to the extent necessary.

However, the agreement does not regulate the operational schedule or procedures of the technical facilities of the spawning site - these are essentially under MOHOSZ's own authority.

The agreement is bilateral, with HNPI (the national park directorate) - although having interests in the area - not being a contracting party. Nonetheless, due to its statutory mandate, HNPI has jurisdiction in nature conservation matters and therefore holds substantial influence over how the site is managed.

In developing the Fokorúpuszta agreement, the Dobai agreement and the current informal operational experiences can serve as a starting point, while also considering the inclusion of several additional aspects during finalization, as mutually agreed upon by the parties involved.

- The technical facilities required for the operation of the spawning site are available; they are currently owned by the Hungarian State and managed by KÖTIVIZIG. Their operation would be transferred to the Anglers' Association, and it is necessary to clarify the responsibilities and obligations this entails.
- A difference compared to the Dobai agreement is that this new agreement would not be tied to a grant-funded project, and therefore the maintenance period is not a determining factor. Instead, the contracting parties must set the duration of the agreement. It would be logical to define a longer period, potentially a decade or more, which could also encompass renovation tasks and responsibilities—terms that would likewise need to be agreed upon.
- As noted earlier, the national park authority (HNPI) has statutory powers, which it can exercise as needed. However, to facilitate smoother operation, it may be worthwhile to establish regular consultations among the three parties. If there is mutual intent, this can be formally included in the agreement.
- The technical operation schedule (see section 6.4) may be included in the agreement, but it is not mandatory.
- We consider it important to have regular monitoring of the spawning site's functioning. The parties may consider including expectations and objectives related to monitoring within the agreement.
- KÖTIVIZIG could undertake to share hydrological forecasts related to flood waves with the operator in advance, thereby supporting optimal timing decisions for opening the structures.
- It may be worthwhile to clarify which party is responsible for repairing damage to the facilities that cannot be attributed to either side (e.g. sediment deposition caused by a flood).

7 Conclusions

Based on our analysis, the active operation of the Fokorúpuszta spawning site is advantageous from both a fisheries and a nature conservation perspective. While its operation primarily serves the interests of the Anglers' Association, its implementation also affects conservation interests. Therefore, consultation and close cooperation with the national park are essential.

The spawning site can partially replace the stocking of fish fry. Considering fish reproduction, the spawning site appears to be more cost-effective on average over several years than purchasing fry from fish farms beyond the mandatory quantities. Thus, operating the Fokorúpuszta spawning site is economically beneficial for the Anglers' Association. Additionally, ecosystem services valuable to local communities and society at large are created, further strengthening the rationale for operating the spawning site. These services include providing habitat and food for protected species, groundwater recharge through infiltration, and cooling summer temperatures through evaporation.

According to economic calculations, even successful spawning every 3–5 years makes the operation cost-effective. However, the role of costs is crucial, highlighting the importance of simplified operational agreements and the ability to respond efficiently to hydrological information.

Importantly, the above conclusions hold only if the initial investment cost is not borne by the anglers' association. The opportunity to establish a semi-natural fish spawning habitat emerged as a by-product of a floodplain realignment project. In this context, wetland restoration as a nature-based solution was publicly funded primarily for its regulatory service in flood mitigation, not for supporting fish spawning. While it makes economic sense to operate the already established fish spawning habitat, there does not seem to be a business case for developing new habitats from private funds. Moreover, any supplementary spillover effects (e.g. local tax revenue, employment opportunities) are minimal and do not change the conclusions on the economic merit of establishing new semi-natural spawning sites. These results also highlight the need for innovation in small-scale, low-cost solutions that can deliver the desired ecosystem services. The management of the Óballa and Bivaly-tó spawning sites may also hold promise, but further investigation is needed—particularly in the case of Bivaly-tó, where the investment costs of the necessary technical infrastructure for the spawning site are significant.

To actively operate the Fokorúpuszta spawning site and clarify the associated responsibilities, it is essential for KÖTIVIZIG and MOHOSZ (or KÖTIHESZ) to reach an agreement. Preparations should start as soon as possible so that upcoming flood waves can be used to support fish spawning. As in the case of the Dobai agreement, we believe the use of the area could be granted free of charge to the Anglers' Association.

The optimal method for operating the site is not yet fully developed. Answering a few basic questions could improve the efficiency of its operation. Targeted experimentation—such as introducing mature spawning pairs, selective release to filter out invasive species, and enhancing hydromorphological diversity in the river to support native species—is essential. Furthermore, regular monitoring must play a central role. Monitoring should include the reproduction of fish and other aquatic organisms, the composition of juvenile populations, and impacts on the ecological status of surrounding water bodies.

Floodplain grazing is beneficial for all stakeholders, especially around spawning sites where manure promotes the growth of plankton that serve as food for fish. As the land manager, KÖTIVIZIG should continue striving to lease as much of the floodplain as possible for grazing or mowing purposes.

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